
**The investigation of Telehealth Services Impact on Improving the Quality of
Life for Elderly –high Risk Patients:
Case of Bahrain's Primary Healthcare Sector**

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Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Background

Telehealth in primary health care has remained controversial in recent studies, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic breakout, which significantly changed our lifestyle and social interaction. It is essential to underline that this subject has become a central axis of World Health. These advances and improvements in consultation and telecommunications have been shown to improve accessibility to health services without the need to see doctors in hospitals when there always remains a risk to grasp coronavirus infection for elderly patients. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Bahrain Ministry of Health adopted the best strategy for delivering uninterrupted medical -care services to all populations, anytime and anywhere (*Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020*).

Health care industries manipulate ways of delivering health services to cope with the current pandemic to protect patients' health and medical staff. So many health care services shifted from face-to-face to virtual interaction (Steindal et al., 2021). Many policy changes have influenced telehealth uptake during the current time, including the evolution of virtual medication prescription, consultation, education, and counseling. The National Health Regulatory Authority (NHRA) in the Kingdom of Bahrain provides a map of relevant policies for integrating digitalization in primary health care. To ensure patients grasp the proper supervision by the right team at the right time by issuing licensing to practice telehealth for primary health care physicians and health professionals that adhere to international guidelines.

Telehealth gets remarkable acceptance by the population after numerous worldwide global primary health clinic promotional guidance(Chang et al., 2021). Governmental primary care in Bahrain started to lead the pack with the ***choose your doctor program*** in June 2018, which allows citizens and residents to meet their doctors using video or phone calls with the expectation of complimentary meetings regarding Covid-19 and the early detection program. A virtual emergency clinic for high-risk Covid -19 was conducted in primary health care in Bahrain on regular appointments for the clinical interview following guidelines in treating patients during quarantine.

Recently, the Supreme Council of Health in the Kingdom of Bahrain has targeted all the government health establishments to move towards autonomy and health insurance schemes. The

focus of the government of Bahrain is on the new government plan to meet Economic Vision 2030 and on achieving sustainable development goals (*Sustainable Development*, n.d.). Primary health care in the Kingdom of Bahrain is developing new strategic plans for automation in terms of administration and monetary support which refers to the hospital's ability to determine its preferences and translate those preferences into authoritative actions (Cimperman et al., 2013). Therefore, the hospital's logistics and departments introduced a broad concept of change management that requires a critical observation of patient needs and expectations to handle all the possible obstacles that affect the quality of healthcare service delivery.

1.2 Signs and symptoms

The ageing population in the kingdom of Bahrain is suffering from chronic diseases (Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020), increasing the demand for care from Bahrain's Primary Health Care service (PHC). The elderly population now requires more long-term care, management, and intervention than ever to sustain their quality of life (QoL), directly increasing the costs of care provision. This is further impacted by a rise in the number of hospital visits for minor complaints due to ageing or chronic disease, which in turn increases the burden on PHCs, patients, and their families.

There is a need for a novel approach to health care management within PHCs that relies on fewer human resources and combines health and social care services more innovatively than at present. Telehealth technologies are considered one such approach for the care of the elderly who have a high level of need and require long-term health care to extend independent living through pre-emptive care interventions, such as health education and timely interventions when deterioration in their well-being is detected. Such interventions aim to reduce the need for hospitalization, reduce recovery time, and positively affect general health and QoL, all while decreasing costs for PHCs (Chang et al., 2021).

Telehealth provision in Bahrain was minimal prior to the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic in 2019. Since then, as social restrictions have limited daily life, interest in and demand for telemedicine provision has increased drastically (Gokalp et al., 2018). Policymakers, insurers, and health professionals responded with rapid strategies to implement and expand requirements to deliver care to patients at home and reduce virus transmission. However, a lack of diagnostic equipment (e.g., blood pressure monitors) and training for patients to look after themselves creates

challenges for the elderly in using innovative technologies to enhance QoL (Gajarawala & Pelkowski, 2021).

1.3 Problem Statement

The elderly population in Bahrain has complex health comorbidities and polypharmacy, and their social and health complications, at an individual and community level, increase the burden on PHC. Between 2019 and 2020, the elderly population increased from 2.52% to 2.7%, respectively, with an average life expectancy in 2020 of 77.7 years (Bahrain Population (2022) - Worldometer, n.d). This increase brings a significant rise in the prevalence of chronic diseases (Healthcare, n.d.), which requires innovative technology to support monitoring, evaluation, intervention, and early detection and to decrease dependency on the PHC. In turn, this requires the elderly to be able to both access and competently use health-related technology to improve their QoL (Wong et al., 2022). Figure 1.1 presents the distribution of the elderly population in Bahrain based on the national census and demographic statistics in 2020.

Figure 1.1 Elderly Population in Bahrain

The level of independence amongst the elderly may decrease further if they have a disability resulting from aging and chronic disease, which creates a further burden on the PHC as

patients require help for minor complaints.

Telehealth technologies have previously been considered for delivering care to the elderly, who highly demand the care service. These technologies have been focused on patients who require long-term health care and on extending the period of independent living through timely interventions when deterioration in their well-being is detected.

Across the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region and Bahrain, there is a lack of data from previous empirical studies assessing telehealth services used by elderly high-risk patients. There is, however, strong empirical evidence from other countries worldwide describing the impact of telehealth services on elderly patients' quality of life (QoL). This study will address the importance of telehealth services in improving the elderly's quality of life in multiple dimensions.

1.4 Research Questions

This research seeks to answer the following research question: What is the Impact of telehealth services in improving Quality of Life for elderly high-risk patients?

Further sub-questions converge from the research question:

- To what extent does telehealth affect elderly mobility?
- To what extent does telehealth affect self-care for elderly patients?
- To what extent does telehealth affect usual activity for the elderly?
- To what extent does telehealth affect pain or discomfort for elderly patients?
- To what extent does telehealth affect anxiety or depression in elderly patients?
- To what extent do elderly patients accept the use of telehealth?
- To what extent do the elderly trust the use of telehealth systems?
- How available are the network and devices for elderly patients?

These questions will be answered in this research.

1.5 Research Goal

The goal of this study is to explore the impact of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their quality of life.

1.6 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to explore the impact of elderly high-risk patients on their quality of life achieved by using telehealth. Further sub-objectives are also taken into consideration:

- To evaluate the opinion of the following QoL dimensions achieved by telehealth:
 - ✓ Elderly mobility.
 - ✓ Self-care for the elderly.
 - ✓ Usual activity for the elderly.
 - ✓ Self-care for the elderly.
 - ✓ Pain or discomfort.
 - ✓ Anxiety and depression for elderly patients.
- Assessing the usability and acceptability of telehealth by elderly patients,
- Assessing the availability of the network and devices for elderly patients and
- Determine the trust in the usability of telehealth by elderly patients.

1.7 Significance of the study

As elderly telehealth should reduce the development of complications and the number of deaths among the elderly, there is a need to raise awareness of using telehealth as a tool to detect diseases in their early stages and achieve changes in self-management and lifestyle among patients with chronic diseases in order to reduce the burden on the health system. Additionally, the results should help program developers better understand how to adapt telehealth to suit the elderly.

1.8 Research Structure

The following chapter provides an overview of Bahrain's telehealth system and the various types of telehealth services utilized in geriatric care, focusing on the quality of life of older high-risk patients and the impact of telehealth on QoL. The third chapter demonstrates the survey methodology and study design used to collect and analyze data. This is followed by a detailed chapter that uses descriptive and inferential statistics and MAXQDA software to illustrate the survey's findings. The fifth chapter thoroughly examines all findings, summarizes the research, makes recommendations, and discusses the study's limits and future research. The study is concluded in the final chapter.

Figure 1.2 Literature Review Mapping

توزيع المؤسسات الصحية حسب المحافظات Distribution of Health Institutions by Governorates

Government Health Centers Ministry of Health
1 - Al Dair
2 - National Bank of Bahrain
3 - Muharraq
4 - Sh. Salman
5 - Hooraa
6 - Ibn Sinna
7 - Al- Razi (Workers H.C.)
8 - Naim
9 - Sh. Sabah Al-Salem
10 - Bilad Al-Kadeem
11 - Jidhafs
12 - Budaiya
13 - Hamad Town
14 - Kuwait
15 - Mohammed bin Jassim Kanoo
16 - AAli
17 - Isa Town
18 - Sitra
19 - Hamad Kanoo
20 - East Riffa
21 - Jaw & Asker Clinic
22 - Zallaq Clinic

Government Hospitals
Geriatric Hospital
Muharraq Maternity Hospital
Saimaniya Medical Complex
Psychiatric Hospital
Jidhafs Maternity Hospital
West Region Maternity Hospital
Sitra Maternity Hospital
Military Hospital
Riffa Maternity Hospital

Private Hospitals
American Mission Hospital
Ibn Al - Nafees Hospital
Bahrain Specialist Hospital
Gulf Dental Speciality Hospital
Dr. Tariq Hospital
Noor Specialist Hospital
Urology & Plastic Surgery Hospital
International Hospital of Bahrain
Awali Hospital

المراكز الصحية الحكومية وزارة الصحة
1 - الدير
2 - بنك البحرين الوطني
3 - المحرق
4 - الشيخ سلمان
5 - الحوراء
6 - ابن سينا
7 - الرازي (ملاج العمال)
8 - النعيم
9 - الشيخ صباح السالم
10 - بلاد الكديم
11 - جد حفص
12 - الدبع
13 - مدينة حمد
14 - الكويت
15 - محمد بن جاسم كانو
16 - عالي
17 - مدينة عيسى
18 - ستره
19 - حمد كانو
20 - الرفاع الشرقي
21 - عيادة جو وعسكر
22 - عيادة الزقاق

المستشفيات الحكومية
مستشفى رعاية المسنين
مستشفى المحرق للولادة
مجمع السلمانية الطبي
مستشفى الطب النفسي
مستشفى جد حفص للولادة
مستشفى المنطقة العربية للولادة
مستشفى ستره للولادة
المستشفى العسكري
مستشفى الرفاع للولادة

المستشفيات الخاصة
مستشفى الإرسالية الأمريكية
مستشفى ابن النفوس
مستشفى البحرين التخصصي
مستشفى الخليج التخصصي للأسنان
مستشفى الدكتور طارق
مستشفى نور التخصصي
مستشفى جراحة المسالك البولية والتجميل
مستشفى البحرين الدولي
مستشفى العوالي

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

A rapidly growing elderly population has made healthcare resources challenging to access and scarce (Jensen et al., 2019). One approach to mitigate this challenge has been the introduction of telehealth medical care services which provide healthcare resources through a range of telecommunication tools and is an innovative strategy designed to improve the shortage of health services (Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020).

Healthcare framework systems globally are facing significant challenges Munford et al. (2020), such as an increased number of patients presenting with multiple chronic diseases which require a complex response over a prolonged period. These typically require collaboration from numerous health professionals, ideally encompassing patient empowerment and helping professionals to coordinate care continuity. Implementing remote monitoring strategies for providing healthcare, such as telehealth, is an example of these challenges.

Telehealth services that utilise health information and communication technologies enable the exchange of data between professionals and the provision of patient diagnosis, management, and ongoing monitoring, particularly in the case of elderly patients with chronic conditions (Gadeikienė et al., 2021). Telehealth has also been implemented to support regular follow-up between patients and healthcare providers has also been implemented. Telehealth's common point of remote care is to enable early intervention, prevent deterioration of long-term conditions, reduce the frequency of secondary care use, and prevent advanced complications (Jiang et al., 2022).

The diagnosis and treatment of the elderly with comorbidities can lead to psychological and physical side effects, such as depression and anxiety. These side effects can challenge the socio-economic structure of many countries in terms of the costs associated with elderly medical care and wellbeing (Zhang et al., 2020). Anxiety and depression, for example, are related to an increased consciousness about safety, environment, nutrition, personal hygiene, adherence to medication, lifestyle, and physical activity. Likewise, elderly patients with comorbidities and disabilities may suffer from increased fear and nervousness, leading to functional impairments and

cognitive dysfunction, resulting in reduced QoL (Larson et al., 2020). These side effects, coupled with a global increase in life expectancy, create challenges in providing healthcare services to the ageing population (Steindal et al., 2021).

As the elderly population grows and the prevalence of long-term, chronic illnesses increases, telehealth is gradually being used to support and enable the elderly to remain at home and independent (Watson et al., 2021). Elderly patients have become one of the major target groups for telehealth technologies, which focus on improving patients' memory and mobility (Teoli & Bhardwaj, 2021). Telehealth for the elderly contributes to limiting the growth of complications and reducing the number of deaths amongst the ageing population (N. Chen & Liu, 2022). As noted by Leite et al. (2020), there is a need to expand awareness of the risks, achieve changes in self-management and lifestyle among patients with chronic diseases, and further develop admittance to incorporated illness administrations, allowing them to function independently in a friendly home environment (Leite et al., 2020). Telehealth supplements chronic disease management within the formal health care framework by developing patient self-awareness and knowledge via “expert patient” programmes (Riu et al., 2018,p1). The ageing process will, in parallel, escalate the implementation of telehealth missions to encourage patients to improve their QoL (Morley, 2021).

The proportion of older adults within Bahrain’s population is rising. It continues to be a significant consumer of health care services (Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020), with the PHC the main provider of preventive and curative medical and social services to the elderly. Providing high-quality care can both improve their health and QoL, thus decreasing the need for extended care and hospital admission.

The elderly are often associated with diseases that burden society, high mortality rates frequent hospitalization (Guo et al., 2021). Often dealing with unresolved symptoms, including dyspnoea, pain, fatigue, anxiety, loss of appetite, depression, and sleeping disorders, their health can deteriorate if these symptoms are not adequately managed (Hullick et al., 2022). Active engagement in self-care can reduce deterioration, enhance the quality of life, and improve the functional capacity of the elderly (Kuerbis & Behrendt, 2020).

This chapter includes three sections; the first will discuss telehealth definition, evolution, and utilisation. The second section will discuss the quality of life for elderly high-risk patients, including definitions, models, and a systematic review of articles related to the effect of telehealth

on elderly QoL, and the third section will provide information about the impact of telehealth services on the main domains of European QoL, and experiences of telehealth worldwide and within the Gulf region.

2.2 Telehealth: definitions, concepts, and evolution

2.2.1 Definition and concepts of telehealth

Telehealth is defined as the exchange of medical health information through innovative telecommunications technology to support health-linked services and disease management across geographic, health promotion, social, time, and cultural barriers (Gadeikienė et al., 2021). It includes offering health care at a distance and utilising technical artefacts to mobilise data representations about patients' (Finn et al., 2021). Larson et al. (2020, p106) define telehealth as “Telehealth technologies, such as telephone, videoconferencing, and internet-based interventions,” which “have the capability of bringing services into the survivors’ home and bolster the management of symptoms without needing to have direct physical contact with the hospital or clinic services” to enhance treatment care from hospital to elderly home to empower themselves with their families to play a more active role in accomplishing health care dialogue.

Snoswell et al. (2021, p292) describe telehealth as “the delivery of health-care services, use of technology to deliver health services at a distance where distance is a critical factor, by all health-care providers using information and communication technologies (ICT) for the exchange of valid information for the treatment, prevention and diagnosis of illness and injuries, research and evaluation, and for the continuing education of health care providers, all in the interests of advancing the health of individuals and their communities.” These aspects have become highly evident in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic situation. The emphasis on preventive care needs and patients’ expectations requires delivering medical services of the highest quality to positively affect patients’ health and engage them as active co-creators of their well-being (Adams & Ecker, 2021). However, telehealth cannot exist without technological innovation as it relies on technology such as radio, telephones, and video to deliver health services at a distance rather than face-to-face setting (Craig et al., 2016). The technological innovations adoption in health care can be seen today

as “the land of opportunities” (Gadeikienė et al., 2021, p1424).

Adams & Ecker (2021, p 476) state that telehealth is defined by the American Academy of Family Practice and “refers to a broad collection of electronic and telecommunications technologies and services that support at-a-distance healthcare delivery and services. Telehealth technologies and tactics support virtual medical, health, and education service”.

Telehealth is considered one of the ways to achieve optimum quality of care and the rapid exchange of medical data and information to satisfy the patient's needs and achieve better treatment results. The increase in the ageing population presents challenges to social care and healthcare, particularly chronic disease prevalence amongst the elderly and the need for long-term management, which are increasing healthcare costs (Raja et al., 2021). Furthermore, the degree of independence amongst the elderly may drop due to disability resulting from disease complications, cognitive ability, and ageing. All previous factors may undermine their autonomy and increase dependency on health care providers and social services (Gokalp et al., 2018).

As telehealth practices, including telemedicine, tele counselling, tele coaching, and tele nutrition, have an impact on the different dimensions of elderly QoL (physical, social, psychological, environmental, overall quality of life, happiness, and satisfaction), this thesis explores the impact of telehealth on elderly high-risk patients with Bahrain’s PHC where many have chronic diseases which affect their physical and psychological health, reducing their QoL (Kaveh et al., 2021).

2.2.2 Evolution of Telehealth

Telehealth is an established setting that has a long history. It started as an electronic medical communication that occurred during the American Civil war (Martin-Khan et al., 2017). The union army used the telegraph as the first tool of telehealth to organise injury patients' transportation and request medical equipment supplies (Nesbitt & Katz-Bell, n.d). In Australia, in 1874, the military used the telegraph to link a dying man with his wife and give care to a person with a cut wound (Frehse, 2021). In 1879, The Lancet described the telephone as a means to reduce unnecessary office visits by listening to the mothers of children complaining of coughs, allowing doctors to listen to and diagnose causes of cough by telephone. In 1925, radio doctors were developed to provide care for sick patients over a distance (Gogia, 2020). Then, home monitoring developed more in the Mercury space program when the National Aeronautics and Space Administration

(NASA) started monitoring physiologically over a distance and providing health care to astronauts (Nesbitt & Katz-Bell, nd)

According to Morley (2021), telehealth started in hospital-based telemedicine in the late 1950s and early 1960s at Nebraska Psychiatric Institute and Norfolk State Hospital to provide psychiatric and neurological services. In 1967, Boston's Logan International Airport used a television broadcast channel with a specialised camera to link nurses and patients with physicians at Massachusetts General Hospital (Groom & Faan, 2021).

Currently, video visits are practised in outpatient care models, chronic care treatment programmes, and remote monitoring solutions (Banbury et al., 2018). Approximately every clinical role now uses telehealth as a modality, including nurses, physicians, physical therapists, speech therapists, diabetologists, and social workers (Graham & Jones, 2020). Physicians in both generalist and specialist roles progressively deliver telehealth services, which helps to optimise their effectiveness and interaction with patients (Immanuel Tonapa et al., 2021). In Denmark, telehealth is widely practised, and patients can take photographs of their wounds and upload the image to a specialist who can prescribe medication (Cichosz et al., 2019). Patients can swallow video capsules supported by a camera connected to telehealth without any harm or discomfort from undergoing a colonoscopy (Kjeldsted et al., 2021). Moreover, portable digital pumps supported by telehealth are available for aleukemic patients to receive chemotherapy services at home (Di Ciaccio et al., 2020,p668).

In the Kingdom of Bahrain, Telehealth gets remarkable acceptance from the population after numerous worldwide global primary health clinic promotional guidance (Chen et al., 2021). Bahrain's PHC introduced the choose your doctor program in June 2018, which allowed citizens and residents to contact their doctors and follow up with critical laboratory tests as required.

In March 2020, during the pandemic, a virtual emergency clinic, a one-stop-shop for high-risk Covid-19 patients, was introduced in Bahrain's PHC for regular appointments, where clinical interviews followed guidelines for treating patients during quarantine Doraiswamy et al.(2021) Before the Covid-19 pandemic, there was less acceptance of telehealth (Peixoto et al., 2022) as patients preferred traditional health care facilities. Telehealth has presented a means to reduce contact with the virus during the pandemic and has prompted researchers to consider new scientific, technological, and innovation findings (Valdivieso, 2018). Countries like Bahrain have shifted their focus to sustainable development goals, encouraging health industries to rethink

policies and business models. People have gained faith in science and technology, showing a greater acceptance of digitalization in health education and treatment of their illnesses (Gogia, 2020).

In December 2015, a greenfield hospital development in Abu Dhabi used telehealth to provide “bread and butter” services, including laboratory, neurology, ophthalmology cardiology, respiratory, and pathology services to ensure access to medical services (Mirza et al., 2018, p1025). This aligned with the country’s Economic Vision 2030 of a long-term sustainable goal to support the health care system, with the former president, Sheikh Zayed bin Sultan Al Nahyan stating, “I had many dreams. I dreamt of our land keeping pace with the growth of the modern world” (Mirza et al., 2018, p1023).

2.3 Telehealth services used in geriatric care

Dhakal et al. (2020) explore telehealth services to support access to health and medical information and improve health care providers' communication with their patients. These services model conventional roles, with the health professional as an expert providing education, assessments or monitoring, and patient participation in reporting any new signs or symptoms. These models support elderly individuals to sustain independent living and promote and prolong autonomy and QoL for the ageing population.

Telehealth consultation in a PHC setting may include a range of services:

2.3.1 Telemonitoring

Health monitoring for the elderly is a significant concern in many countries where older individuals are taken into clinics or hospitals for basic health care solutions and treatment for well-being therapy (Chen et al., 2022). Through the telemonitoring process, patients capture their health condition through event-based monitoring by comparing the health data obtained from wearable sensors in each data transmission cycle with the data from the previous cycle and share vital signs such as glucose level, blood pressure, heart rate, and temperature to a professional at a remote facility. For example, The professional can adjust insulin doses linked to blood sugar levels (Lopez-Liria et al., 2019). Thus, older individuals can remain in their homes without health concerns (Dhakal et al.,2020).

Telemonitoring helps suggest preventive maintenance, predict disease, and track physical health activity such as heart rate, body mass, temperature, drug administration, and oxygen saturation by examining the elderly patient's medical history and identifying any health difficulties. Additionally, assistive technology (such as safety sensors exists to help older people with cognitive impairments by ensuring that they remain safe, perform the necessary tasks, and monitor their mental status.

The Federal Food and Drug Administration approved wearable devices after guaranteeing the reliability and quality of remote patient monitoring (RPM) (Fishpaw & Zawada, 2020). Morgenthaler (2021) also suggests that RPM technologies are increasingly efficient in improving chronic disease management, post-acute care, and continuous monitoring relating to the safety of the elderly. Their studies have shown that these advancements can help older adults slow the progression of chronic diseases such as diabetes, asthma, heart disease, and chronic hypertension. However, Jiang et al. (2022) noted that telehealth innovation programmes are complicated for the elderly due to technical learning difficulties.

Elderly individuals with diabetes mellitus who receive multiple insulin doses through insulin pump therapy should self-monitor blood glucose levels throughout the day, as American Diabetes Association recommends. Self-monitoring blood glucose is part of an educational programme that professionals can provide through telehealth to guide treatment decisions and self-management (Buse et al.,2020). Despins & Wakefield (2020) have noted that individuals share blood glucose monitoring graphs from elderly sensors and transmit data through regular intervals to healthcare personnel devices that adjust diet and medication and provide feedback to keep them healthy.

2.3.2 Tele-coaching

Tele-coaching is a health programme that provides health-related information, encouragement, or recommendations to the patient regularly or when required. Health coaching includes encouragement, feedback, health concern suggestions, periodic health instruction, guidance, or short educational videos based on an analysis of the elderly health condition. An example of a tele coaching message is sleep pattern management advice if the patient is not sleeping (Markert, Sasangohar, et al., 2021b).

2.3.3 Tele-medicine

Doraiswamy et al. (2021, p3) and Kruse et al. (2020, p2) summarised the definition given by WHO Tele-medicine and presented telemedicine as “the delivery of health care services, where distance is a critical factor, by all health care professionals using information and communications technologies for the exchange of valid information for the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and for the continuing education of health care providers, all in the interests of advancing the health of individuals and their communities.” Leite et al. (2020, p 483) defines telemedicine as “healing from a distance.” More specifically, it is healing through the use of information with communication technologies “to improve patient outcomes by increasing access to care and medical information.

2.3.4 Tele-exercise

Tele-exercise includes managing the patient's risk profile, for example, helping the elderly live in a community in which fall prevention intervention is more effective due to falling prevention programmes and exercises which strengthen walking and balance based on the Otago exercise programme (Giordano et al., 2016; Khemapech, 2019). Additionally, that exercises strengthen walking and balance, again based on the Otago exercise programme, support the elderly to live more safely within the community.

2.4 Opportunities for telehealth

Telehealth provides health support services, analyses health usage trends, provides information to authorised professionals, enhances communication technologies, offers affordable and technical feasibility, and improves access to home care health services (Steindal et al., 2021; Zulfiqar et al., 2019). It effectively reduces hospital admissions that directly correlates with social cost, length of hospitalisation, and better quality of life for the elderly (Steindal et al., 2021). Opportunities for telehealth include the following uses:

As a preventive and promotional tool - Telehealth provides a new requirement opportunity to promote and support long-distance clinical health care and education, from first response to recovery with extensive coverage and low cost (Markert, Moon, et al., 2021). The previous research by Leite et al. (2020) and Karlsen et al. (2019) showed that telehealth might reduce family caregivers’ perception of task-specific burdens and improve feelings of relief which is important in decreasing the stress that family caregivers may experience. As one of the most

important benefits of preventive medicine is to reduce the feasibility of the disease in the early stage (Donaghy et al., 2019), Telehealth enhances recovery of symptoms such as fatigue; supports pain management, sleeping, fear, and diminishes aggressive treatment with comorbidities, with the effectiveness of telehealth found to be beneficial in reducing mortality due to chronic diseases (Raja et al., 2021).

Healthcare equality and the safety of the elderly –are additional benefits, linking clinicians and clients at geographically varied locations through enhanced communication, reducing possible transportation barriers, and providing accessibility for health services. Early implementation of telehealth for the elderly with life-threatening illnesses will improve patients' and their families' satisfaction, improving the quality of life for the elderly (Lang et al., 2022). Furthermore, feeling secure is a fundamental requirement that enables the elderly to stay healthy (Watson et al., 2021). The experience for elderly patients is supported by health care providers who share the responsibilities of managing their sickness (Steindal et al., 2021), with people worldwide easily connected to health care services (Jiang et al., 2022). According to Howland & Wakefield (2021), introducing evidence-based telehealth practices across formal clinical and non-clinical settings enhances decision-making to achieve operational excellence and facilitate strategic competitive advantage to strengthen hospital best practices.

To enhance innovation capability in health industries - advantages to initiative innovation via good management to guide health industries to respond in a timely and quick manner and constant progression of health activities through leadership best practice and being flexible with the process and product innovation (Krittawong, 2021). Organisational capabilities are complex skills and knowledge patterns that, over time, become embedded as corporate routines, developing research interest for growth and success to create innovation in the long term. Studies have shown that telehealth can improve and strengthen internal control capabilities, cooperation between health departments, and enhanced system and development capabilities (Jiang et al., 2022).

Continuity of care - provides continuity of care and easy follow-up by physicians. Digital healthcare facilities reduce costly visits to the emergency room and improve patient expectations and satisfaction with health care services (Gardenier et al., 2021). As more patients retire, families depend on these services to care for their elderly loved ones. Telehealth contributes to the green agenda and sustainability goals with lower carbon dioxide emissions by reducing the need to travel

for health services. Implementing telehealth supports telehealth progress, which is encouraged by public authorities due to its benefits to improving the accessibility of health services, the collaboration between professionals, optimised use of health provider time, enhanced care pathways, and stimulates innovation in the therapeutic management plan (Zulfiqar et al., 2019).

Cost reduction - Research by May et al. (2021, p483) indicates that telehealth positively influences the coordination of the health organisation, and financial savings and facilitates “healing at a distance” for patients separated geographically. Digital healthcare facilities reduce costly visits to the emergency room and improve patient expectations and satisfaction with health care services (Graham & Jones, 2020). Due to the acceleration in the timely care of patients, physicians can conduct teleconsultations when they might otherwise have been moving to or from home, thus increasing their capacity for delivering care. Telehealth also effectively reduces hospital admissions, directly correlating with social cost, length of hospitalisation, and better quality of life for the elderly (Steindal et al., 2021).

Educational tools - Studies by Kruse et al. (2020) and Adams & Ecker (2021) show an initial effort involved in learning to use telehealth technology. Smith (2021) suggests educating patients about their illness and lifestyle could be accelerated due to the deficiency of medical staff and health care professionals, especially in an emergency situation. Therefore, the telehealth platform could be used as an educational tool for sharing knowledge and experiences. Additionally, telehealth improves workload among health care providers and decreases job burnout (Chang et al., 2021).

Service Diversity - With digital technology advancements in multimedia streaming and data type, a variety of telehealth services, including tele-pharmacy, tele-physiotherapy, telemedicine, and telenursing (Khemapech, 2019).

Fighting diseases during the crisis - Gutierrez et al. (2021) investigate telehealth during pandemics as circumstances provoke increased fear and panic and urge people to obtain help across public healthcare systems, modelling service waves that trigger additional difficulties for the service ecosystem, such as overloaded emergency departments in hospitals, which struggle to handle extraordinary demand and constrained capacity. This develops into a vicious cycle, according to Almallah & Doyle (2020), who concluded that more attendance of patients in emergency departments produces even more contamination in populations. Steindal et al. (2021) revealed that practising physicians may be reluctant to implement telehealth due to reduced quality

of care, loss of personal communication & connection with clients, liability concerns, privacy worries, and shortfalls in reimbursement appliances. However, Adams & Ecker (2021) concluded that the Covid-19 pandemic enhanced the rapid adoption of new care systems, with telehealth proficiency becoming an essential clinical skill for practising professionals and trainers.

Additionally, Telehealth allows the health care provider to be “on-call anytime night or day” and to monitor telehealth patients so that anticipatory care may be provided before an illness occurs (Graham & Jones, 2020, p234). Telehealth-based care services offer many benefits for the elderly as they can remain in their home environment and feel comfortable and safe (Béland et al., 2022), with the comfort of knowing they are under constant monitoring, this positively impacts their sense of security and quality of life (Alhuwail et al., 2022).

2.5 Barriers to the use of telehealth

Understanding telehealth barriers, Kalicki et al. (2021) suggest that the usability of telehealth care services amongst elderly individuals is the main barrier to using telehealth technology. The elderly are often stereotyped as laggards in the adoption and acceptance of technology due to obstacles such as self-confidence, access to technology, interest in its use, and macro-level barriers to access, such as software access, funding, and policy standards (Lopez et al., 2021; Donaghy et al., 2019). The main obstacles are described as follows:

2.5.1 Implementation of technology

Implementation of telehealth includes different domains before execution, such as developing other teams in managerial and technological fields to study infrastructure resources, patients’ needs, and digital technology software and hardware. Moreover, there is a need to develop the next generation of telehealth solutions and devices that meet future requirements (Gajarawala & Pelkowski, 2021).

Many other concerns are present, including regulatory, human resources, legal issues, and successful implementation of telehealth services (Gogia, 2020). There is a significant disagreement in Bahrain’s telehealth licensing laws and policies (Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020). Current rules generally refer to the patient’s physical location as the place of service, regardless of

the provider's location. Moreover, kingdom laws typically require that health care professionals be licensed and hold their credentials at their place of service. According to Kruse et al. (2020), although telehealth positively impacts patient outcomes and satisfaction, providers face many obstacles when integrating telehealth practices. Regulations and laws governing health care provider practice and health insurance reimbursement standards for telehealth vary broadly and often obstruct the use of telehealth in practice. Providers need to comply with best-practice regulations that struggle with using digital technology. Obtaining and upholding licensure for telehealth is also a barrier.

Gajarawala & Pelkowski (2021) note that when establishing telehealth services, these must align to strategies in place to meet patient expectations and satisfaction and meet guidelines interconnected with laws to ensure patients' safety in telehealth practice, such as preventing physicians from prescribing controlled substances.

Adams & Ecker (2021) observe that telehealth practice is governed by codes of ethics for health care providers. Concerns include the erosion of the provider-patient relationship, patient confidentiality, privacy, and security (Donaghy et al., 2019).

2.5.2 Usability of technology.

Kalicki et al. (2021) report that telehealth technology is transforming care delivery modalities as health providers expect telehealth use, which plays a pivotal role in achieving improved quality of care. The health care entity embraces various health technologies and moves to its maturity (e.g., telehealth services) as health providers need to recognise and understand components of the telehealth system skills, such as exchanging electronic data from one site to another and using a wide variety of modalities in telecommunications, such as conferencing for interactive two-way communication, store-and-forward systems to exchange recorded health information. Steindal et al. (2021) demonstrated that telehealth systems' lack of expertise affects stakeholder interest, with efficient work structure a significant constraint to telehealth's successful adoption and implementation.

Under these circumstances, Kruse et al. (2020) conclude that clinical and educational programmes can raise health providers' familiarity with telehealth skills. Prior studies (Lin et al., 2018; Newbould et al., (2021) observe that including technology and telehealth skills within the curriculum for medical students increases professionals' confidence in using technologies,

enhances medical students' virtual communication skills with shared clinical practice standards and increases physician behaviours and perceptions toward technology.

2.5.3 Digital Technology Acceptance

Kalicki et al. (2021) consider that while many digital technologies integrate into daily life, the elderly still have an issue with acceptance (Lang et al., 2022). Studies of telehealth adoption among primary health care patients have confirmed the complex interplay of client-level barriers to access, such as self-confidence, individual interest, technology access, macro-level obstacles to access software, and some issues such as security and privacy (Lopez et al., 2021; Donaghy et al., 2019).

Zhou et al. (2019) consider users' acceptance of ICT-based health services, such as conceptualised telehealth, where engagement amongst older patients' is particularly challenging due to a traditional reluctance to accept innovative solutions. Understanding elderly users' decision-making and behaviour in the context of telehealth innovation presents the greatest challenge in successfully implementing telehealth acceptance and commercialisation. Cibaroğlu et al. (2021) review the ideas of Davis (1986), who described a Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) where the adoption of new technologies by individuals depends on Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEoU). The model establishes the success of information systems not evaluated by managerial and technical qualifications but includes changes in the users' personal characteristics, expectations, and perceptions that may primarily affect adoption success. The theoretical foundations of this model underlying the TAM are primarily predictive, simplistic, comparable, and robust.

The TAM consists of several causal relationships. Perceived Usefulness (PU) is defined by Cibaroğlu et al. (2021) as the possibility that an individual takes forward technology productivity in an organisational context by using new technology to enhance job performance; a high PU score would indicate that patients believe in positive use-performance relationship. Perceived Ease of Use (PEoU) is described as the level of individual belief where users can eliminate mental and physical efforts by using a particular system. This model expects PEoU to show a significant, immediate influence on PU. Attitude towards Using (AtU) indicates the level at which a citizen is interpreted to control the use of the target system in work (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Behavioural Intention to Use technology (BI) is an estimate of the power of a person's intention to perform a

particular behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), and Actual System Use (ASU) refers to the direct use of a specific system individually. Therefore, it is a powerful and dynamic behavioral criterion, which is goal-repetitive, specific, non-specific to action, context, and timeframe (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

Zhou et al. (2019) describe new technology that widely innovated life and drastically changed patients' lifestyles. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed to accelerate advances in computer innovation technology and used to justify and predict elderly acceptance of new information technology. External factors were also used in the model to influence user beliefs and perceptions to ensure the successful implementation of new technologies. Information technology plays a critical role in healthcare services; due to the population ageing and rising trends in instances of chronic disease, requirements for long-term health care have increased in quality and quantity. Therefore, there has been increased emphasis on integrating information technology and health care.

Studies by Cimperman et al. (2016) assess the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) as the latest spinoff of TAM. This model was adopted by Venkatesh et al. (2003) and examined extensively in many fields and promises to be a magnificent tool for evaluating users' acceptance of telehealth technology.

The final construct in the UTAUT model is Behavioural Intention to Use (BI) which, as defined by Cimperman et al. (2016, p4), is “a measure of the strength of one’s intention to perform a specified behaviour.” Four significant constructs influence this, these being effort expectancy (EE), performance expectancy (PE), facilitating conditions (FC), and social influence (SI).

The UTAUT model is typically supplemented with additional contextual constructs that integrate particular elements of the field of use, such as the addition of the physician-patient relationship constructs or the social capital factors (institutional trust, social trust, and social participation). Establishing additional contextual predictors enables an accurate understanding of different users' acceptance of technology, which is constantly domain specific. Based on the research by Zhou et al.(2019) into acceptance amongst elderly patients toward health technology, three context-specific predictors were added to the original model, namely doctor’s opinion (DOC), computer anxiety (CA), and perceived security (PS). As a result, the augmented model contains two groups of predictors: universal (technology acceptance) predictors and context-specific predictors.

Zhou et al. (2019) review theories about technology acceptance in their study. As the TAM is the leading theory in health services ICT acceptance investigation, TAM has developed to become a fundamental model in predictors of human behaviour toward potential acceptance or rejection of telehealth technology. The UTAUT, developed from the TAM model, has been extensively tested in various aspects and ensures an excellent tool for analysing users' acceptance of health technology (Cibaroğlu et al., 2021)

2.5.4 Network Disparity & Elderly Trust

Kalicki et al. (2021) observed that amongst adults living in New York, USA, 42% of adults aged over 65 were without broadband internet access, compared to 23% of adults aged between 18 to 64 years. This disparity in the availability of internet access is influenced by many factors, including unemployment, geographic location, and poverty. Therefore, older adults may struggle to use electronic devices to access internet services such as telehealth. May et al. (2021) suggest that poor internet network connectivity can negatively impact the quality of telehealth consultations due to delays in transmitting health information from primary healthcare physicians to patients.

Tsai (2014) proposed that the social capital model is an aggregate of actual or potential resources interconnected to control a durable network of relatively institutionalised relationships of a mutual acquaintance. Halford (2012) highlights that Bourdieu adopted this model in 1985 and offers good ability in expecting people's behaviour in utilizing a new technology. Cimperman et al. (2016) stated that social capital includes several aspects of social structure and facilitates specific actions of individuals within the system. Corvo (2020) summarised that social capital contains features of social structure, such as social trust, networks, and norms, which facilitate cooperation and coordination for mutual benefits. Tsai (2014) argues that social capital involves the trust, information, and norms of mutuality inherent in social networks. Corvo (2020) and Tsai (2014) defined the social capital model as the sum of the potential and actual resources embedded within a network of relationships maintained by an individual and social unit.

Social capital can be considered a facilitator of social structure for definite actions of individuals, which is an advantage for both organisations and individuals, relating mainly to interactions between people. Social capital mostly measures patient trust or social networks and social participation. Patient trust explores individual expectations or institutions acting fairly,

openly, competently, and considerately. Tsai (2014) explored that patient trust could be divided into vertical trust in the institutions of society (institutional trust), generalised trust in other people (social trust), and horizontal trust. Within the healthcare industry, institutional trust will enable patients to trust healthcare providers without any personal knowledge of the health workers.

Trust amongst elderly patients in health care professionals (i.e., social trust) is associated with the technical or clinical competence of the health provider, interpersonal quality of health services, and concern for the citizens rather than the disease only. Furthermore, patient trust in the health care industries (i.e., institutional trust) also encourages the use of services, patient compliance, and submission to treatment (Corvo, 2020)

The purpose of telehealth is to improve older adults' ability to remain in their homes as long as possible, with support services enabling them to do this safely with easy access to care. Trust allows residents to believe that the health care professional or the health institution (hospital) has enough ability, integrity, and benevolence to deliver expected positive outcomes. Similarly, trust facilitates patients to believe that healthcare providers or the health institution will provide the required support and assistance (e.g., consultants, professional staff, user guide handbook, and training courses) to improve the ease of use of telehealth technology (Tsai, 2014).

2.5.5 Physical impairment of elderly

The elderly may suffer from a physical impairment that gradually deteriorates with the ageing process, such as vision, cognition, dexterity, hand-eye coordination, and computer anxiety (Lang et al., 2022). Furthermore, Kruse et al. (2020) explored further challenges faced by the elderly, suggesting some individuals may struggle with difficulty seeing, hearing, or speaking and lack a consistently available caregiver to assist with a telehealth visit.

Some barriers related to the design of electronic devices include poor colour contrast, small font size, and the need for fine motor skills when navigating electronic devices to use video telehealth. To overcome these challenges and expand telehealth facilities to the elderly population, high assistive qualities such as automatic information transmission, fewer buttons, and joint audio and visual guidance are required. Moreover, the lack of technical literacy is a significant concern, as many elderly individuals already have issues using technology to check emails (Khemapech,

2019).

2.5.6 Artificial intelligence to support telehealth

Samal et al. (2021) identify self-management support, including artificial intelligence, that empowers the elderly to take an active part in their health, improving their self-efficacy and quality of life. These remote patient monitoring devices can facilitate interaction between citizens and health care providers by remotely monitoring medication adherence and physiological data such as weight, blood pressure, cardiac rhythm, and oxygen saturation with messages to the primary care physician through telehealth.

Graham & Jones (2020) summarise that using artificially intelligent devices such as sensors, health and monitoring wearables, and voice-activated devices is challenging for older individuals. Their research describes how some seniors without any cognitive impairments were challenged by confusing, hard-to-decipher user interfaces and complicated, multi-stage installation and operation processes of the sensors. Moreover, ill-placed buttons and keys increased misuse, particularly for those with arthritic fingers or significantly sensitive touchscreens, increased misuse.

Compounding this, instructions written in small font describing a multi-step process made it hard for those with an ageing vision to read. Additionally, wearables sensors often rely on features requiring quick actions that frustrate the elderly. Papoutsis et al. (2020) argue that artificial intelligence is costly equipment at the initial stages.

2.6 Impact of the Patients in Using Telehealth

“Patients’ perception of care quality refers to patients’ view of services received and the results of the treatment and are monitored to assess the delivery and quality of healthcare, while patient experiences is a reflection of what actually happened during the care process”(Gishu et al., 2019,p 1).

Improving healthcare services quality has become a significant objective for health organisations and health schemes worldwide to identify the patient need to improve poor health services, meet patients' expectations for quality healthcare services, and manage costs. Existing literature, and hospital practices in health services, reinforce the notion of hospitals improving quality and enhancing patient safety through the adoption of quality measurement systems(

Henderson et al., 2013; Greenhalgh et al., 2015). Patients' expectations and perceptions about the quality of health services provided by hospitals is crucial element affecting patient outcomes, profitability, outcomes, performance, and effectiveness.

With the rapid hospital growth of health care services, it becomes essential to know the patient perception of service delivery's responsiveness, reliability, empathy, and assurance (Akdere et al., 2020). service quality is only measured through dimensions of the customer perceptions rather than their expectations to improve medical practices that will enhance patient outcomes, increase the effectiveness of primary care, and control costs (Finn et al., 2021).

2.7 Quality of Life of the Elderly High-risk patients

Healthcare providers focus on improving the quality of life for elderly patients outcome. As P et al. (2019) discuss in their research, each health care organisation must choose strategies that are most suitable for patients to ensure the provision of telehealth communication technology. The ageing population poses a challenge for the healthcare industry due to increased expenses for multimorbid elderly patients with complex needs. This shifting dynamic of the elderly demographic changes over time and develops acceptable and effective care innovations to allow the elderly to live as healthy for as long as possible. This section will discuss the definition of QoL, different models, elderly phenomena, and their QoL.

2.7.1 Quality of life definitions and models

The World Health Organisation (WHO) refers to QoL as “individuals’ perceptions of their position in life in the context of the value systems and culture in which they live, and concerning their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns” (WHOQOL, n.d). International interest is enhancing the focus on QoL amongst the elderly population due to increasing numbers of elderly adults and higher life expectancy.

QoL, defined by Teoli & Bhardwaj (2021), is a concept that aims to capture individual well-being, observing both positive and negative elements within the entirety of their existence at a specific time. For example, standard features of QoL include personal health (physical, spiritual, and mental), relationships, work environment, social status, education status, wealth, a sense of safety and security, freedom, social belonging, and their physical surroundings and autonomy in decision-making. The Quality-of-Life Research Unit at the University of Toronto defines QoL “as

how much a person can enjoy the valued possibilities of their live” (Teoli & Bhardwaj, 2022,p 234).

WHOQOL – BREF is an abbreviated version of 26 items from WHOQoL-100 containing an assessment developed by the WHO and published in 1995, created from a multidimensional perspective of QoL (Skevington et al., 2004) applicable to varying circumstances and cultures worldwide. It assesses how people function across various living environments (Table 1), creating four QoL domains: physical health, psychological, social relations, and environmental.

Table 2.1 WHOQOL-BREF domains of quality of life

Domain	Facet	Question number in the WHOQOL-BREF
Global items	The overall quality of life	1
Health	General health	2
	Pain and discomfort	3
	Dependence on medicinal substances and medical aids	4
	Energy and fatigue	10
	Mobility	15
	Sleep and rest	16
	Activities of daily living	17
	Work capacity	18
Psychological health	Positive feelings	5
	Spirituality, religion, and personal beliefs	6
	Thinking, learning, memory, and concentration	7
	Bodily image and appearance	11
	Self-esteem	19
	Negative feelings	26
Social relationships	Personal relationships	20
	Sexual activity	21
	Social Support	22

Environmental Quality of life	Freedom, physical safety, and security	8
	Physical environment (pollution/noise/traffic/climate)	9
	Financial resources	12
	Opportunities for acquiring new information and skills	13
	Participation in and opportunities for leisure/recreation/ activities	14
	Home environment	23
	Health and social care: Accessibility and quality	24
	Transport	24

(“Development of the World Health Organization WHOQOL-BREF Quality of Life Assessment. The WHOQOL Group,” 1998).

The capability approach in Adult Social Care Outcomes Toolkit (ASCOT) from Netten et al. (2011) can be used to assess the effects of telehealth use on the elderly’s ability to live the life they choose. The ASCOT is designed to capture information about a person’s social care-related QoL (SCRQoL). It is a novel designated method to determine the impact of services telehealth services and evaluate domains of QoL that could be affected by social care. Created in June 2010 after several studies by the ASCOT group in the UK (Studies BSc & MSc, n.d.), Netten et al. (2011) discuss Sen’s 1985 analysis of social capital and capabilities measures individuals’ control and choice concerning social care rather than functioning, while ASCOT emphasises individuals’ capabilities.

Table 2.2 ASCOT: Main guidance, v.2.1 (Netten et al. 2011)

Domain	Definition
Control over one’s life	Ability to choose what to do and when to do it. Having control over daily activities.
Cleanliness and comfort	Being clean, dressed, and groomed to the level that the person feels comfortable and presentable.

Food and drink	Have enough food and drink which is nutritious, varied, and culturally acceptable.
Personal safety	Feeling safe and secure, free from abuse, harm, or failing.
Occupation	Sufficiently occupied with a range of meaningful activities.
Social participation and involvement	Content with social interactions with family friends and feeling part of the community.
Accommodation cleanliness and comfort	Cleanliness and comfort of the home environment.
Dignity	The psychological impact of using social care services according to the user's sense of significance.

The Euro Quality-5 Dimension model is a generic instrument that evaluates HRQoL developed by EuroQoL-Group (EuroQoL Group, 1990). It is widely used in European countries and consists of five dimensions, mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain & discomfort, anxiety, and depression. It fills the gap in information related to HRQoL and social values of health conditions (Kind et al., 2005).

Table 2.3 Main Domains of European QoL(EuroQol Group, 1990)

Main Domain	Definition	Author
Mobility	Movement by walking, driving, and biking	(Marten et al., 2021)
Self-Care	Brushing hair, washing, dressing, and toileting	(Marten et al., 2021)
Usual Activity	Social participation, reading, and praying.	(C.-F. Lin et al., 2020)
Pain/ Discomfort	An unpleasant emotional and sensory experience associated with potential or actual tissue damage for older adults for more than three months. Pain is also related to complications associated with gait abnormalities, deconditioning, accidents, cognitive decline, and polypharmacy,	(Kaye et al., 2010)
Depression/Anxiety	Loss of elderly self-esteem (powerlessness, helplessness, and alienation), loss of meaningful roles (work productivity), declining social contacts owing to health limitations, and decreased functional status. Worries about their life, death, and health.	(Marten et al., 2021)

EQ-5D model was chosen for our study as it is designated for simple self-completion by older people, and patients engage in assessment of their health in an approach that is reliable, valid, systematic, and easy to pick up elderly health issues that they neglected (Devlin et al., 2020).

2.7.2 Elderly High-Risk Phenomena, Definitions & QoL

An increasingly ageing population is a worldwide phenomenon that will destabilise public health in the future; as health care services expand, as does the required budget, with life expectancy continuing to increase worldwide (Morley, 2021). As the percentage of the Bahraini elderly population increases from 2.52% to 2.7% in 2019 and 2020, respectively (MoIA, 2021), this percentage is expected to increase in the coming years due to increased life. Increased life expectancy will concern health authorities to delay the onset of diseases, frailty, functional decline, and loss of autonomy. An increased number of elderly will increase usage of the health care system. Between 2015 and 2050, the proportion of the world's population aged 60 years will double, from 12% to 22% (WHO, n.d.). In 2019, those aged 60 years and above represented almost all medical expenditure and a high proportion of drug expenditure (MoIA, 2021).

Doraiswamy et al. (2021) emphasise the importance of designing person-centered healthcare services to improve the QoL amongst the elderly population. This population has a high prevalence of multimorbidity and needs care that is person-centred and coordinated, thus ensuring the successful implementation of innovative strategies in an age-friendly healthcare system. Dhakal et al. (2020) identify one of the critical priorities for healthcare providers and governments worldwide to postpone dependency and disability in later life by adopting hospital-based patient portals that can engage elderly patients in their care. The healthcare industry is now being encouraged to focus on meaningful use of online access for the elderly, so they may engage in their care management, allowing coordination of their care by their health professionals.

Orimo et al. (2006, p149) define the elderly as being of a “chronological age of 65 years old or older, while those from 65 through 74 years old are referred to as “early elderly,” and those over 75 years old as “late elderly.” The United Nations (UN, n.d.) and the WHO (WHO, n.d.) define the elderly as a person aged 60 years, this aligning with the definition within Bahrain, declaration law number (58) for 2009 (Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020).

In terms of the definition of elderly high-risk patients, according to the European

Association of Prevention Cardiology (Statistics of Chronic Diseases 2021, n.d.), high risk is defined as presenting single or multiple factors such as familial dyslipidaemia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus (type 1 or type 2), cardiovascular diseases, and moderate kidney diseases, these being the leading causes of death and disability. A complication of these diseases in older aged patients includes hearing loss, refraction errors, joint and muscle pain, depression, and dementia Kalicki et al. (2021). Older age presents complicated chronic diseases that lead to several complex health states commonly referred to as geriatric syndromes. They are often a consequence of multiple underlying factors, including urinary incontinence, frailty, falls, pressure ulcers, and delirium (Cartwright et al., 2013).

Kaveh et al. (2021) describe the elderly as susceptible to suffering from social isolation, interaction, and loneliness, highlighting factors contributing to this such as social isolation, lack of social network, feeling of loneliness, and less participation in social activities. In a systematic review conducted by Renaut et al. (2015) evaluating loneliness in the elderly with chronic diseases like heart diseases, diabetes, and hypertension, a strong link was found between chronic diseases and loneliness, a serious global phenomenon. Older people who live alone with a lack of social support and isolation are more prone to low self-rated health and depression and become less independent with daily activity, with significant physical and mental problems that lead to unstable personal relationships.

According to research by Snoswell et al. (2021), the main markers for improving QoL are access to good healthcare, meaningful work or volunteerism, making time for enjoyable hobbies, loving relationships, good rest, healthy food, and performing an enjoyable exercise. Additionally, studies have found that practising meditation, gratitude, and treating mental health disorders can enhance QoL. Holmqvist et al. (2014) recommend adequate sleep to improve both QoL and healthier control over mood and energy levels.

2.7.3 Impact of telehealth on elderly quality of life

According to research, the elderly with comorbidities are a global health-related problem due to more severe and prolonged diseases. The resulting consequences can be a substantial rise in health care utilisation, health care costs, physical function impairment, and poor QoL. Telehealth enables the elderly to live independently at home and has had a significant impact on improved QoL. It makes people feel they are still their own person, with intrinsic value, able to make their own

decisions and maintain regular physical and social activity(Gokalp et al., 2018). Telehealth services accelerate the detection of abnormal patterns in vital signs and prompt interventions to prevent worsening of health. The services enhance the feeling of activity engagement and participation from the elderly and support long-term retention, bringing remote social care and health together to keep the elderly independent.

Table 2.4 Review of articles related to the impact of telehealth on elderly QoL.

Telehealth Services (TS)	Authors, year	Research	Impact of TS on QoL
Telehealth &Tele-exercise	(Giordano et al., 2016)	A two-group randomized controlled trial for elderly high-risk patients, tele-exercise intervention to test group.	Improve the physical functional status of the elderly by reduction times of fall /6 months, progress improvement in gait and balance & QoL (EQ-5D).
Telehealth	(Damant et al., 2017)	Scoping review of published literature 2007-2014 for elderly used telehealth technology.	Greater sense of elderly independence and control over their daily lives, positive sense of freedom, and positive impact on mobility and QoL.
Telemonitoring	(Lopez-Liria et al., 2018)	Elderly patients with heart diseases with two groups of test and control groups in Nordland Hospital.	EQ-5D VAS* ¹ & Minnesota living with heart failure questionnaire significantly improve baseline HRQoL.
Telehealth & telemonitoring	(Gokalp et al., 2018)	Thirty-six (36) patients aged 82 years with congestive heart failure (CHF) & chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) received telehealth intervention.	Improved health care and have a positive impact on the well-being of the elderly.
Telehealth	(Valdivieso et	Effect of telehealth support	Using EuroQol (EQ-5D)

¹ Visual Analogue Scale is a tool helps elderly to rate the intensity of feeling and sensation by recorded self-rated health status on a graduated (0-100) scale with highest score reflect higher HRQoL

	al., 2018)	on quality of life using EuroQol (EQ-5D) instrument for 472 elderly high-risk patients.	instrument. Equality of life -5D score was significantly higher in the telehealth group compared to traditional care in these dimensions (mobility, self-care, performance of daily activities, pain and discomfort, and anxiety and depression).
Telehealth	(Zhou et al., 2019)	436 elderly through multi-stage cluster sampling.	Accessibility of information & acceptance.
Telehealth	(Platts-Mills et al., 2020)	RCT of 360 elderly patients with musculoskeletal pain provided with educational video through telehealth.	Control pain.
Telehealth	(Barenfeld et al., 2020)	2 focus groups of twelve elderly patients with heart diseases and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases.	The intervention group with telehealth showed a positive impact on self-management and accessibility of information.
Tele coaching	(Tonapa et al., 2021)	A systematic review of twelve published studies on RCTs between 2006 and 2020. Represent of 1934 with heart failure patients.	Improve self-care behaviour and quality of life in patients with heart failure in the intervention group compared to the control group.
Telehealth & Tele-coaching	(Markert, Sasangohar, et al., 2021)	A systematic review of 13 studies was published between 2014 and 2019; for elderly individuals above 65 years.	Improve QoL, behaviour change, control blood pressure and blood sugar, and improve daily physical activity and user acceptance.
Telehealth & Telemonitoring	(Samal et al., 2021)	Systematic reviews and Meta-analyses of 44 published articles between 2010-2020.	Empower the elderly through self-management support, monitoring vital signs, care coordination,

			and decision making. Improve care process, clinical & QoL outcome.
Telehealth, telemonitoring, and tele exercise	(Kwak et al., 2021)	113 elderly aged 60 years and above with type 2 DM with test and control group in an experimental study.	Significant reduction in total calorie intake and body mass index. Increase DM control and improve QoL using a disease-specific instrument (DQoL) with a positive impact on (physical functioning, body pain, general health, social interaction, emotional and mental health support). Acceptability to use technology & feeling happier.
Telemonitoring	(Lang et al., 2021)	Two groups of elderly with comorbidities such as depression and cognitive impairment used the telemonitoring application for one group.	Mental cognitive scores significantly improved with elderly who used TMA (telemonitoring application).
Telehealth	(Watson et al., 2021)	Semi-structured qualitative interview for elderly, family carers, and service commissioners.	Improve QoL and decrease the stress of both the elderly and service providers.
Telehealth	(Kaveh et al., 2021)	A systematic review of 18 studies containing 8273 elderly patients with DM.	Telehealth positively impacts cognitive function, psychosocial support & QoL.

2.8 Telehealth services impact on the main domains of European QoL.

This section discusses the impact of telehealth services on the main domains of European QoL and telehealth experiences worldwide and within the Gulf Region.

2.8.1 Mobility, pain, and discomfort

Platts-Mills et al. (2020) discuss how older adults are particularly at risk of chronic conditions such as (musculoskeletal pain) with a significant reduction in physical function and increased risk of falls and injury. This leads to a higher dependency on opioid medication, opioid overdose, and opioid use disorder. Observational studies Platts-Mills et al. (2020) and Giordano et al. (2016) suggest using the Shared Decision Making Model through telehealth in PHCs during an acute situation for the elderly suffering from musculoskeletal will improve pain recovery treatment and increase patient satisfaction. Conversely, less education for the elderly on controlling their diet and exercise enhances medication administration and lowers the QoL of patients with chronic diseases (Kwak et al., 2021).

Additionally, Platts-Mills et al. (2020) review the use of video telehealth education, emphasising active elderly engagement. Telemedicine should educate patients about the common classes of user pain medication to relieve muscle pain (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, acetaminophen, and opioids) and discuss recovery-promoting behaviour (physical activity, social support, sleep, and relaxation breathing). Telehealth educational programmes have a significant impact on improved sleep, anxiety, depression, muscle pain, and decreasing medication dependency on opioids (Beer et al., 2021).

Several studies reported large proportions of older people (Watson et al., 2021; Giordano et al., 2016) use telehealth for fall prevention programmes (tele exercise), resulting in improved QoL, balance, gait, and decreased risk of fall mobility. Electronic devices to provide remote monitoring greatly influence a person's mobility or activities of daily living (ADLs), such as preparing a meal, bathing, driving, cleaning home, and dressing (Markert, Sasangohar, et al., 2021).

Watson et al. (2021) consider that telemonitoring could improve confidence and safety amongst the elderly. As ageing progresses and health deteriorates, conditions such as heart diseases or depression can increase, making individuals more likely to spend more time in bed. This indicates poor adherence to medication and a general worsening of the patient's situation. Their research suggests a type of ADLs monitoring for medication adherence which can be monitored remotely through automated pillboxes that can be used to organise medications, offer reminders to adhere to medication schedules, and deliver patients' information to professionals via

telehealth regarding medication use to enhance mobility and ADLs.

Ni et al. (2016) suggest that daily activity by using particular types of sensors and artificial intelligence in telemonitoring for diabetic elderly patients in their homes significantly impacts confidence and independence to perform ADLs.

Telemonitoring ADL could improve elderly care by enhancing a sense of safety and mobility QoL. There is a strong relationship between mobility and elderly physical health. Saragih et al. (2021) suggest that mobility and tele-exercise improve muscle and bone pain and make the individual less susceptible to falls or fractures. The Systemic review by Saragih et al. (2021) found that combined tele exercise with virtual reality training improved motor function by reshaping elderly skills and mobility balance, which affect ADL performance.

Evidence suggests that using telehealth for the elderly population has significantly enhanced their sense of control over daily life and independence. In their research, Watson et al. (2021) reported that older people interacting with their professionals in tele coaching sessions through their own telehealth devices feel a sense of freedom and independence. Moreover, Chen & Schulz (2016) discussed how the elderly practice opens online meetings and exchanges emails with health providers to increase their sense of control, dependence, and learning new skills. Studies by Kruse et al. (2020) argue that there is a decrease in the sense of control amongst those who use a computer only.

2.8.2 Self-Care

Under the ageing phenomenon, offering the elderly a sense of personal safety and security is a fundamental goal of telehealth. Giesbrecht & Miller (2019) highlight the greater importance of the elderly learning skills and using wheelchairs through telehealth as educational material used in PHC setting, reflecting more greater elderly mobility patterns and potential benefit of cognitive and motor function in tele-exercise following instruction and using their muscles to participate in community-based activities and overcome environmental barriers such as safety, and empowering elderly with self-efficacy, confidence, independence and learning new skills. Beer et al. (2021) found that tele-exercise increases patients' skills and empowerment. Kruse et al. (2020) also found that 96% of participants favoured telemonitoring services that ensured personal safety in their homes. Steindal et al. (2021) reported high ratings of feeling safe and secure in daily life amongst the elderly who received telehealth. Watson et al. (2021) found that people receiving fall detection

telehealth and lifestyle monitoring services reported improved feelings of safety compared to people without such services.

Several studies (Steindal et al., 2021 and Dhakal et al., 2020) reported that the elderly population who own an electronic device to contact their professionals for emergency use have a positive sense of personal safety. Conversely, Gajarawala & Pelkowski (2021) discuss cybersecurity that affects patients' safety and privacy during telehealth consultations due to suspicions that “Big Brother was watching” (Guinemer et al., 2021,p2). Their research espoused concerns about the elderly becoming victims of abuse or crime when using telehealth as important information may be shared with third parties, resulting in a negative effect on their sense of security.

Tonapa et al. (2021) reported that tele-coaching trends conduct educational programs that enhance self-care behaviour, confidence, continuity of care, and active engagement to decrease symptoms and improve QoL. Additionally, tele-coaching encourages active communication between health care professionals and patients, builds trust, and motivates patients to adhere to their medication and improve QoL. Markert, Sasangohar, et al. (2021) suggest tele-coaching based on behavioural change theory includes a wide variety of education, goal setting, suggestion, encouragement, periodic health tips, and feedback on health-related conditions. For example, massage in sleep management coaching decreases depression and anxiety for elderly patients. Pillboxes to organise their medication and a reminder to take it regularly saw improvement in elderly pain and discomfort, impacting physical, mental, and psychological health.

Kwak et al. (2021) reported that telemedicine increases access to health care services for sick, older people with chronic diseases living in rural areas, with positive reflection in HRQoL as telemedicine provides early treatment and steady intervention, and accessibility of health, social and mental services. Telemedicine promotion programmes offer a solution to access to healthcare for the elderly and medically vulnerable patients in a comfortable home. Barenfeld et al. (2020) support access to patients' information, facilitate communication and provide interactive access to digital platforms if the patient desires to invite friends, family, other patients with the same medical illnesses, and other professionals.

2.8.3 Usual activity

Elderly found access to interaction with a health care professional this experience will elaborate

on the category of “being welcomed through the side door when lacking the front door keys” to gaining support, help, and concern interaction through positive reinforcement (Barenfeld et al., 2020, p 5). To share and participate by own skills in active engagement to address their fear, worries, and health plan, identify social support from a caregiver at home and extend to community social activity participation.

Kwak et al. (2021) consider that the involvement of family members, friends, or patients with similar conditions in telemedicine to discuss experiences of illnesses, medication, and side effects positively affect elderly social activity participation. Controversy research by Chung et al. (2021) regarding social involvement and participation in telehealth raises concerns about the reluctance of the elderly population to give up the human touch provided through face-to-face consultations, supported by Ordaz et al. (2021), who notes that the elderly can deliberately formulate false alarms to support social contact with care specialists.

Banbury et al. (2017) suggest that telehealth counselling adds value in providing accessibility of services, skills, and knowledge to enhance group communication processes such as cohesiveness and bonding social support. Steindal et al. (2021) conclude that telehealth consultation and health care professionals are major sources of information. Patients with close families feel confident asking questions and sharing decisions about their health conditions and social interaction by keeping in touch with others. Markert, Sasangohar, et al. (2021) discuss that social isolation makes individuals more prone to developing depression, stress, hospitalization and has a higher mortality rate than those who are socially engaged with their professionals via a digital platform.

Lang et al. (2021) and Beer et al. (2021) suggest that telemonitoring and tele exercise amongst elderly patients support role in elderly mobility. It improves muscle strength and stamina, enabling the elderly to perform a wide range of daily activities, thus improving their physical and psychological well-being. Gokalp et al. (2018) observe that based on vital sign measurements, including blood sugar and blood pressure, the elderly can enjoy a sense of safety knowing this information is being shared with their health professional, allowing them to live independently at home while continuing their daily activities

Newbould et al. (2021) research suggests that the elderly who participate in a wide range of social, informational, and emotional digital networks have significantly improved disease-self management. Newbould et al. (2021) also reference the effectiveness of interactive social support

in tele-coaching to the elderly via interactive corporate programs such as support groups, discussions, and chat rooms, significantly improving their psychological safety and usual activity. Echoed by Raja et al. (2021), elderly online activity involvement through video interaction improves social activity with a significantly reduced risk of loneliness, depression, and suicidal ideation.

2.8.4 Anxiety and Depression

In several studies, Lang et al. (2021) and Egede et al. (2017) describe the direct positive effects of telehealth on older people's QoL and well-being. Egede et al. (2017) convey the enjoyment and a sense of purpose gained from using email and open chat rooms to communicate with loved ones. (Chang et al., 2021). also discuss how the elderly experience a sense of accomplishment, pride, feelings of independence, empowerment, and escalated self-esteem from using the internet and email and participating in telehealth training. The Independent Age report by Kaveh et al. (2021) suggests that older adults feel mentally alert, attentive, challenged, and subsequently more youthful during online activities.

Kwak et al. (2021) innovate that telemedicine improves chronic diseases and psychological and behavioural changes through rapid treatment and early detection to decrease disease deterioration and improve physical health and independence. Lopez-Liria et al. (2019) reported the use of telemonitoring to show a significant decline in depressive status amongst the elderly population with comorbidities. Lang et al. (2021) suggest a significant positive correlation between the use of the telemonitoring application and overall life satisfaction. At the same time, there is a negative correlation between the use of telemonitoring and depression. Kruse et al. (2020) consider that remote telemonitoring provides alert services which are helpful (rather than unhelpful) in enabling older adults to feel optimistic concerning their future and reducing the severity of anxiety and depression. Beer et al. (2021) conclude that tele-exercise classes improve physical, psychological, and emotional function.

Tonapa et al. (2021) found that the elderly population interested in or using a tele-coaching service significantly declined in anxiety at baseline compared to those not using or interested in the service. Markert, Sasangohar, et al. (2021) found significantly higher senior optimism levels in older experience telehealth users than non-users.

Henderson et al. (2013) concluded that telehealth and telecare services have no significant

effect on anxiety or depression symptoms from baseline throughout 12 months follow-up. Indeed research by Kruse et al. (2020) suggests that the elderly decrease their mental acuity with telehealth because the computer is too complex, needs a fine touch, and good eye-hand coordination, which accelerates their computer anxiety.

Lang et al. (2021) consider the elderly with mild cognitive impairment and depression are negatively associated with QoL. The elderly population with comorbidities who engage with telehealth significantly increases their mental function QoL. Kruse et al. (2020) pointed to telehealth interventions as the reasons for a substantial decrease in psychological distress (reduction of depressive symptoms, anxiety, embitterment, grief, worries, loneliness, increased emotional support, and mood). Conversely, Arnedt et al. (2021) discovered that data from cognitive behaviour treatment with anxiety and depression in randomised control trials throughout 3 to 6 months of follow-up showed superior performance through face-to-face treatment than virtual therapy.

A study done by Leite et al. (2020) suggests that time spent in self-isolation or quarantine can generate a sense of loneliness. Elderly adults who experience isolation or quarantine reported many concerns, such as fear, depression, and anxiety; in some cases, they develop severe symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder. These negative psychological effects can be mitigated through the telehealth platform with a significant reduction in symptoms compared to face-to-face hospital intervention (Aj et al., 2022).

2.9 Experiences of telehealth in other countries Vs. local studies

Valdivieso et al. (2018) assess the effect of telehealth intervention on quality of life and mortality for 472 elderlies with chronic comorbidities in the Spanish region of Valencia. The study was a randomized control, non-blinded trial in a teaching hospital and six primary health centres using the (EQ-5D) instrument. The result showed a high QoL score and improvement among the telehealth group compared to the usual care group. However, there was no significant impact on mortality and emergency admission.

A study in Korea by Kwak et al. (2021) collected data from 113 patients with chronic diseases living in rural areas in a pre-post-test quasi-experimental design to identify the link between telehealth services (telemedicine) and HRQoL (medication adherence, mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain and discomfort, anxiety, and depression) It was found that telemedicine

prompting tool for remission symptom of depression and anxiety. Additionally, telemedicine motivated medication adherence. The result was 1.76 times higher after involving telemedicine compared to hospital care. However, there was no relation between self-care activity and telemedicine.

A systematic review and meta-analysis done by Snoswell et al. (2021) in collaboration with two Australian Universities, Macquarie and Notre Dame, analysed data from 2015 patients from different age groups between 10 - 69 years based on telehealth interventions measuring QoL outcome in patients with bronchial asthma. The evaluation measured intervention between 8 weeks - 30 months and used a disease-specific instrument QoL questionnaire for bronchial asthma. A comprehensive overview was found in the literature that showed no significant statistical difference between age groups, with substantial telehealth improvement in QoL.

In Denmark, the study by Cichosz et al. (2020) assessed the effect of telehealth on HRQoL through a comparison between a control group and a test group of patients with heart failure. Measurement of physical and mental outcomes through follow-up of two groups with insignificant changes in a physical component while significant improvement in mental component score in the intervention group.

Telehealth in Arab countries found a gap in research relating to elderly telehealth and QoL. One study by Khader et al. (2014) on telecardiology application in patients with heart diseases and its impact on QoL, time, and cost-saving, concluded that telehealth significantly impacts the improvement of QoL and helps in diagnosis and treatment plan. In Jordan, in (Queen Rania and Mafraq hospitals) with two-month follow-up of physical functioning, general health perception, bodily pain, role functioning-physical, vitality, social functioning, role functioning-emotional, and mental health for elderly patients, with significant improvement in QoL, access to health care and help in diagnosis and treatment plan for patients.

The present-day analysis found a lack of available innovative research with an apparent disparity in geriatric telehealth and QoL topics in Bahrain and GCC countries; however, many published articles relating to telehealth for elderly patients during Covid-19. A study in telehealth for geriatric care during Covid-19 in Qatar done by Doraiswamy et al. (2021) used a SWOT analysis of telehealth services to identify strengths and weaknesses of the service to cater to the necessities of the elderly and considered the main strengths of telehealth as improving well-being, decreasing the risk of falls, and managing dementia.

2.10 Conclusion

In conclusion, empirical studies reviewed a lack of research into the impact of elderly telehealth on their QoL. All relevant literature related to elderly QoL in different countries like the UK, Australia, Korea, China, and Denmark. The researchers used to identify what hinders in dimensions of QoL model variables from other articles. Nevertheless, the following main research questions remain unanswered and applicable to the national context.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The previous chapter reviewed the literature, including the theories, models, and studies to define and explore the thoughts of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth on their QoL. This chapter aims to explain the methodology roadmap that guides this research and outlines the research problem, objective, conceptual framework, variables, research questions, and hypotheses. The chapter then highlights the research methods applied and the justifications for using these methods. It provides details about the research paradigms, followed by the sampling technique used and the study's sample.

Before collecting primary data, content analysis was used as the research method to determine the knowledge gaps and advantages in creating the research instruments. Consequently, secondary data were collected from extensive range of resources, including academic journals, books, newspapers, health reports publications, statistical documents, and government and health websites.

3.2 Research Objective

The research objective of this thesis is to explore the perception of elderly high-risk patients about using telehealth services on their QoL. To reach the objective of this research, the proposed model, figure 3.2, includes dependent and independent variables from the European QoL & Technology Acceptance Models while moderating variables from the literature review to achieve the objective of this research. A mixed-method approach is used in collecting and analysing data. The thesis methodology map is shown in figure 3.1.

3.3 Research Design and Data Collection

According to Fetters et al. (2013), the research design is a comprehensive outline of the methodological decision taken, as many research designs apply to different researches. However, research design selection depends primarily on the research problem to be investigated. The study presents an exploratory research approach to review the data provided to assess the thoughts of elderly high-risk patients using telehealth on their QoL in primary health care centres. The study design used a mixed methodology – quantitative and qualitative. As Bowers et al. (2013) indicated,

mixed methods are a powerful tool for understanding the impact of complex technology in the healthcare system, confirming the accuracy of the final result and providing insights into the health process. This study is constructed on a survey directed to the patients and interviews related to elderly patients who used telehealth services and family physicians who used telehealth consultations. In this way, the study demonstrates that elderly patients think telehealth with ageing is a problem. The health care provider does not consider elderly telehealth healthcare a challenge; a new conclusion is raised. The result should add to creating change proposals in the health system, and more data exploration will be needed and required. As Chatwood et al. (2015) suggest, combining data types within an analysis requires analysis using the categorical or continuous variables for statistical analysis. Furthermore, to compare coded qualitative data because there is clear reasoning for benefitting such analytic techniques.

Ozawa & Pongpirul (2014) suggest combining different methods in studying new health systems to maximize each approach's strengths and answer questions that are inefficiently answered by another approach. Mixed methods potentially offer a depth of qualitative understanding with the reach of quantitative to gain a more comprehensive picture of understanding of telehealth services. Additionally, view patients' issues with these services and, hear the voices of elderly & health care professionals participants, examine experiences outcomes to capture a macro picture of the health system (Wisdom et al., 2012).

Three data sources in qualitative research develop a comprehensive understanding of phenomena (as patients, Nurses, and health care professionals)—confluence triangulation, as its methodological technique applied to support both validation and competencies of research findings. The triangulation aims to check the validation of the research, “deepening and widening” the researcher's understanding of examining phenomena (Ashour, 2018,p194).

Figure 3.1 shows the study design (Fielding, 2012)

3.4 Conceptual Framework

The research model was established by the Euro-QoL group during many stages of development, as the European group decided to have a comprehensive instrument that involved many descriptive dimensions, including the HRQoL tool, which contains mobility, daily activities, self-care, psychological functioning, social and role performance, and other health problem. In 1988 the generic instrument included 6 dimensions and was developed after several studies of the Euro QoL questionnaire. Theoretically, the group decided to be confined into 6 dimensions: mobility, self-care, main activity, social relationship, pain, and mood (Kind et al., 2005).

In 1990 the QoL model was reduced into five dimensions with three levels, and in 1993 Euro QoL plenary meeting in Netherland approved the final model, which included 5 dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain or discomfort, anxiety or depression. The acceptance and usability of telehealth services by the elderly patients for the telehealth innovation technology are used by patients' adoption theories as to the Technology acceptance model and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Cimperman et al., 2016). In addition to the literature review and other empirical studies, the framework is performed in Figure

3.2.

Relationship among the variables

Figure 3.2 Proposed conceptual model, adopted and adapted from Europe Quality -5 Dimensions model(Euro QoL Group, 1993)and the Theory TAM (Davis, 1989) & UTAUT(Venkatesh et al., 2003) Pg 25.

3.5 Research Questions

What is the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their QoL in Bahrain's primary healthcare? Sub-questions are also added:

- To what extent does telehealth affect elderly mobility?
- To what extent does telehealth affect self-care for elderly patients?
- To what extent does telehealth affect usual activity for the elderly?
- To what extent does telehealth affect pain or discomfort for elderly patients?
- To what extent does telehealth affect anxiety or depression in elderly patients?
- To what extent do elderly patients accept the use of telehealth?
- To what extent do the elderly trust the use of telehealth systems?
- How available are the network and devices for elderly patients?

Figure 3.3 Main Research Question and Hypothesis (Author)

3.6 Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

Null Hypothesis (H1_o): There is no relationship between using telehealth services and elderly quality of life

Alternative Hypothesis: (H1_a): There is a relationship between using telehealth services and elderly quality of life.

Hypothesis 2

Null Hypothesis (H2_o): Using Telehealth services does not affect the mobility dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Alternative Hypothesis (H2_a): Using Telehealth services affects the mobility dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Hypothesis 3

Null Hypothesis (H3_o): Using Telehealth services does not affect the self-care dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Alternative Hypothesis (H3_a): Using Telehealth services affects the self-care dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Hypothesis 4

Null Hypothesis (H4_o): Using telehealth services does not affect the usual activity dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Alternative Hypothesis (H4_a): Using Telehealth services affects the usual activity dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Hypothesis 5

Null Hypothesis (H5_o): Using telehealth services does not affect the pain or discomfort dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Alternative Hypothesis (H5_a): Using Telehealth services affects the pain or discomfort dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Hypothesis 6

Null Hypothesis (H6_o): Using telehealth services does not affect the anxiety or depression dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Alternative Hypothesis (H6_a): Using telehealth services affects the anxiety or depression dimension in the elderly's quality of life.

Hypothesis 7

Null Hypothesis (H7_o): The age of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly mobility.

Alternative Hypothesis (H7_a): The age of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility.

Hypothesis 8

Null Hypothesis (H8_o): The age of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly self-care.

Alternative Hypothesis (H8_a): The age of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly self-care.

Hypothesis 9

Null Hypothesis (H9_o): The age of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly usual activity.

Alternative Hypothesis (H9_a): The age of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and the elderly usual activity.

Hypothesis 10

Null Hypothesis (H10_o): The age of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H10_a): The age of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 11

Null Hypothesis (H11_o): The age of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly anxiety or depression.

Alternative Hypothesis (H11_a): The age of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly anxiety or depression.

Hypothesis 12

Null Hypothesis (H12_o): The educational level of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly mobility.

Alternative Hypothesis (H12_a): The educational level of the user of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility.

Hypothesis 13

Null Hypothesis (H13_o): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between telehealth service use and elderly self-care.

Alternative Hypothesis (H13_a): The user`s educational level of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly self-care.

Hypothesis 14

Null Hypothesis (H14_o): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between telehealth service use and elderly usual activity.

Alternative Hypothesis (H14_a): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly usual activity.

Hypothesis 15

Null Hypothesis (H15_o): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between telehealth service use and elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H15_a): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 16

Null Hypothesis (H16_o): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between telehealth service use and elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H16_a): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 17

Null Hypothesis (H17_o): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between telehealth service use and elderly anxiety or depression.

Alternative Hypothesis (H17_a): The educational level of the users of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly anxiety or depression.

Hypothesis 18

Null Hypothesis (H18_o): The living arrangement of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly mobility.

Alternative Hypothesis (H18_a): The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility.

Hypothesis 19

Null Hypothesis (H19_o): The living arrangement of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly self-care.

Alternative Hypothesis (H19_a): The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly self-care.

Hypothesis 20

Null Hypothesis (H20_o): The living arrangement of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and usual activity.

Alternative Hypothesis (H20_a): The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly usual activity.

Hypothesis 21

Null Hypothesis (H21_o): The living arrangement of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H21_a): The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 22

Null Hypothesis (H22_o): The living arrangement of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly anxiety or depression.

Alternative Hypothesis (H22_a): The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly anxiety or depression.

Hypothesis 23

Null Hypothesis (H23_o): The user's dependency on a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly mobility.

Alternative Hypothesis (H23_a): The user's dependency on telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility.

Hypothesis 24

Null Hypothesis (H24_o) The user's dependency on a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly self-care.

Alternative Hypothesis (H24a) The dependency of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly self-care.

Hypothesis 25

Null Hypothesis (H25o): The user's dependency on a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly usual activity.

Alternative Hypothesis (H25a): The user's dependency on telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and the elderly usual activity.

Hypothesis 26

Null Hypothesis (H26o): The user's dependency on a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H26a): The dependency of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 27

Null Hypothesis (H27o): The user's dependency on a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly anxiety or depression.

Alternative Hypothesis (H27a): The dependency of the user of telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly anxiety or depression.

Hypothesis 28

Null Hypothesis (H28o): The acceptance of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly mobility.

Alternative Hypothesis (H28a): The acceptance of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility.

Hypothesis 29

Null Hypothesis (H29o): The acceptance of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and elderly self-care.

Alternative Hypothesis (H29a): The acceptance of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly self-care.

Hypothesis 30

Null Hypothesis (H30o): The acceptance of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly usual activity.

Alternative Hypothesis (H30a): The acceptance of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and the elderly usual activity.

Hypothesis 31

Null Hypothesis (H31o): The acceptance of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly pain or discomfort.

Alternative Hypothesis (H31a): The acceptance of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and the elderly pain or discomfort.

Hypothesis 32

Null Hypothesis (H32o): The acceptance of the user of a telehealth service does not influence the relationship between using a telehealth service and the elderly anxiety and depression.

Alternative Hypothesis (H32a): The acceptance of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and the elderly anxiety and depression.

3.7 Research Paradigm and classification

The below section clarifies research classification and paradigm according to purpose, logic, outcome, and rationale for each selection; a mixed research paradigm is believed to be applicable

in this study to explore the impact of elderly telehealth users on their quality of life. A mixed-method is best suited when the research aims to determine the opinion of elderly QoL achievement after using telehealth (Bowers et al., 2013).

Additionally, mixed methods used quantitative & qualitative; health services researchers utilized quantitative methodologies to address research questions regarding generalizability, causality, or extent of effects. Qualitative methods are used to research questions to investigate how or why a phenomenon happens, describe the nature of a person's perception, and create a theory (Fetters et al., 2013). Combining quantitative and qualitative data can considerably enhance the value of using mixed methods research; combining the two forms of data can have various advantages. The qualitative data can be used to evaluate the validity of quantitative results (Klassen et al., 2012). Quantitative data can also be beneficial to facilitate the generation of the qualitative sample or illuminate findings from the qualitative data. Moreover, many researchers used mixed methods in innovation technology related to elderly QoL (Steindal et al., 2021; Hullick et al., 2022).

- Classification according to research purpose: the purpose of this research is exploratory design, the researcher will collect and analyse the quantitative and qualitative data, and the final findings will be used to build on the result from the quantitative data collection (Fetters et al., 2013). The quantitative results with qualitative study will clarify relationships discovered in both fields (Klassen et al., 2012).
- Classification according to research logic: the research uses deductive reasoning that is apprehensive with validation of usability of telehealth models and theories testing field (Fetters et al., 2013).
- Classification according to research outcomes: the outcome of a research study can be implemented in an actual health situation. This study will help primary health care improve elderly telehealth positively affect their QoL. It also helps form appropriate plans and strategies to strengthen telehealth technology through a multidisciplinary clinic.

3.8 Quantitative Method

3.8.1 Questionnaire Design

EuroQoL instrument designed based on levels asking elderly patients about their Quality of life. The questionnaire was redrafted and piloted extensively before the final version was produced by

in-depth interviews with patients in different countries to assess comprehensively.

The tool helps health organizations with quantitative research and to understand patients' QoL in any health facility with different health services and technologies. Adapting the EuroQoL instrument aims to add value in improving QoL and life expectancy of the elderly and provide valuable feedback to the hospital board, staff, commissioners, patients, and the public. Not to mention that the EuroQoL group encouraged the researcher to obtain a license to adopt and use the tool in the current research. The EuroQoL Tool consists of five dimensions of HRQoL to evaluate the effect of telehealth in the elderly with the five-dimensional classification; each dimension has four levels for assessing elderly QoL. Telehealth Usability questionnaire was added to increase the power function relationship between the effect of improvement of elderly QoL achieved by using telehealth, to increase valuations to QoL parameters, validity, and reliability of each particular measurement field (Kind et al., 2005). Five Euro QoL dimensions as listed in the table. Each item or question of the survey is coded for statistical analysis.

The online questionnaire consists of and develops three sections as follows:

- Section 1: includes demographic data of the elderly patients, is used as moderating variables, and consists of 9 questions.
- Section 2: include five main dimensions of QoL with four levels, each with a total of 20 items, for the study's requirements and represent the dependent variables.
- Section 3: include usability and acceptance and contains 7 questions on 3 points Likert scale. And it is derived from the Telehealth Usability Questionnaire designated to be comprehensive to cover six usability factors (including usefulness, ease of use, effectiveness, reliability, satisfaction, and future use) of 20 questions in the original version of the questionnaire. Seven questions were selected based on the research objectives. In conclusion, the questionnaire is categorized into three sections; the first includes demographic data, the second section is related to elderly QoL, and the final section comprises usability and acceptability of telehealth technology. In January 2022, a request was sent to the Euro QoL group for a license to adopt the Euro QoL tool for the quantitative method. After accomplishing all the requirements, the EurQoL group does not require licensing for non-commercial use.

Table 3.1 shows the questionnaire items with their references.

Dimension	EQ-5D category	Primary Health care category	Code	References
1 Mobility	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No problems walking about. 2. Practically no problems in / very small problems in / very little problems in walking. 3. Small/slight/minor / somewhat problems in walking. 4. Some problems in / rather problems in walking. 5. Unable to walk about / confined to bed or wheelchair. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It does not affect a patient's mobility 2. Patient unable to move 3. It is helping the patient move more often. 4. It is making the patient move less often 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 2 3 4 	<p>(Kind et al., 2005)</p> <p>(Marten et al., 2021)</p> <p>(C.-F. Lin et al., 2020)</p> <p>(Kunz, 2010)</p> <p>(Valdivieso et al., 2018)</p>
2 Washing or dressing self	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No problems with washing or dressing. 2. Practically no problems with / very small problems with very little problems with washing or dressing. 3. Small/slight/minor / somewhat problems with washing or dressing. 4. Many problems with washing or dressing. 5. Unable to wash or dress self 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patient washes and dresses /herself, and telehealth has no effect on that. 2. Patient unable to wash or dress /herself, and telehealth has no effect on that. 3. It increases the interest of the patient in washing or dressing. 4. It decreases the interest of the patient in washing or dressing 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5 6 7 8 	<p>(Makai et al., 2015)</p> <p>(Persson et al., 2020)</p> <p>(Valdivieso et al., 2018)</p> <p>(EuroQol Group, 1990)</p>
3 Usual activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No problems with usual activity. 2. Practically no problems with / very small problems with very little problems with usual activity. 3. Small / slight / minor / somewhat problems with 4. Many problems with usual activity. 5. Unable to perform 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The patient does their usual activity, and telehealth does not affect that. 2. The patient is unable to do a usual activity, and telehealth does not affect that. 3. It increases the patient usual activity. 4. It decreases the patient usual activity. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9 10 11 12 	
4 Pain or discomfort	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No pain or discomfort. 2. Practically no / occasionally light. 3. Mild pain or discomfort 4. Moderate pain or discomfort 5. Extreme pain or discomfort. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patient does not suffer from pain or discomfort, and telehealth does not affect the pain or discomfort. 2. Patient suffers from pain or discomfort; however, telehealth does not affect pain or discomfort. 3. It increases patient pain or discomfort. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13 14 15 16 	

		4. It decreases patient pain or discomfort		
5 Anxiety or depression	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not 2. Little anxious or depression. 3. Slightly /somewhat anxious or depression. 4. Moderately anxious or depression 5. Extremely anxious or depression. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patient does not suffer from anxiety or depression, and telehealth does not affect it. 2. Patients suffer from anxiety or depression, and telehealth does not affect it. 3. It increases patient anxiety or depression. 4. It decreases patient anxiety or depression 	 17 18 19 20	

The survey adaptation guidance was applied when making the changes. Figure 3.4 illustrates the adaptation process.

Figure 3.4 the adaptation process (Author)

Step One: Some adaptations were made to Euroqol survey questions; for example, amending questions to be more relevant to the thesis subject and connected to telehealth services, additional changes of phrases or vocabulary that were not clear, and using simple words to be understood by elderly patients and shortening the length of questions.

Step Two: Adaptations to the method and mode of data collection. In dealing with elderly high-risk patients, an online survey was distributed on the tablet with a short note about the questionnaire's aim before the elderly started answering the questions. The researcher found many errors when sending the questionnaire through elderly emails, as many questions were incomplete answers. Or using phone-to-phone interviews does not prefer the accuracy of elderly answers. Approval from the health information department and medical records provided the researcher

with patient lists with personal and health information. Like appointment date, the timing of attending the health centre, telephone number, individual ID, comorbidities (diabetes, hypertension, heart diseases, respiratory diseases, and other illnesses), and the number of telehealth services used in the last 12 months. The researcher tried to choose patient samples from different health centres while selecting the population. One health centre was randomly selected from five health regions to avoid redundancy in patient information.

Step three: EuroQoL questionnaire translated into another language as Spain, French, and Arabic by Euro group members; language Translation Framework aims to achieve another conceptually equivalent language version of the English questionnaire. EuroQoL questionnaire emphasised the cross-cultural and conceptual rather than the linguistic/literal equivalence. Therefore, the forward-translation and back-translation methods were used.

The application of this method includes the following phases:

- **Phase one:** Forward translation by a formal English translator to Arabic, emphasising conceptual rather than literal translations and using acceptable and understood language for the vast audience. Real-World Study(RWS) Life Sciences, a trusted British authority, provides linguistic validation and cultural adaptation of elderly patient's in the Management of clinical outcomes assessment (COAs) and has significant experience in this region in a wide-range therapeutic, scientific uses (PR Newswire, 2017).
- **Phase two:** Expert panel: English translator checked by another professional expert and a doctor of linguistics to obtain maximum comprehension of the Arabic language use. The Source version was revised by an in-country language consultant, a native speaker of the target language, and reformation was added as proposed and recommended by the language consultant to ensure that the questionnaire was appropriate for elderly patients. The questionnaire's content reflected the health culture of the GCC community. Easy of self-completed and accomplished survey using shorter sentences with significant interaction between different QoL dimensions.

- **Phase three:** Back translation: emphasising the literature perception. Therefore, the Arabic survey outline final draft was tested by a doctor of linguistics and accepted. The version was examined on 5 Arabic-speaking respondents living in Kuwait, with a spread of socio-demographic qualities and characteristics of both healthy individuals and patients.
- **Phase Four:** The Arabic consultant translator and MoH research committee reviewed the modified version and followed their last feedback in the latest Arabic and English versions, with approval from the research and Ethics committee in MoH (AppendixD&F).
- **Phase Five:** It is important to conduct pre- piloting or cognitive testing before distributing a large-scale survey, particularly when data is collected by a self-administered questionnaire (Pallant, 2020). The questionnaire of this study was subjected to a pre-testing before distributing it. The preliminary testing was made on the layout and formatting, grammar, wording, sequence of questions, and the statements' clarity. The piloting was conducted on a sample of respondents. The online version hyperlink of the questionnaire in a tablet given to 28 elderly patients contains three sections with 36 questions. It provides the participants time to consider their responses carefully without interference from the researcher; using the online survey questionnaire ensures confidentiality for the participants, resulting in more honest and transparent responses. In addition, using an online application simplifies the data analysis phase and benefits the researcher in collecting a large number of responses cost-effectively and swiftly (Beauchet et al., 2014).

The participants were requested to provide feedback about any difficulties or other remarks they faced in filling out the questionnaire. The feedback received was a few confusing words in the questions to the elderly, and overall, the structure was found to be adequate, and the language use was proper. The required changes were made on the final questionnaire using some simple words before commencing the data collection.

A request was forwarded to the health information department in primary care at the beginning of January 2022, asking for around 700 patients' health and personal information from five health centers chosen randomly. The elderly patients have appointments in primary health care clinics such as Diabetic, non-communicable diseases, and general clinics in March and April of 2022. The selected samples from the elderly population used telehealth in the last 12 months and met them to answer the online questionnaire. The patients were randomly selected using a

stratified sampling method to allocate patients from different health centres in different health regions in the kingdom of Bahrain; verbal consent was taken before conducting an online survey.

3.8.2 Survey Sampling Design

Primary Health Care elderly patients who attended selected health centres during March and April 2022 were eligible to answer the questionnaire. The elderly population was defined as high risk with one or more diseases and used telehealth services in the last 12 months.

Primary health care medical records provided information on 700 patients, presenting the research population as requested. The sampling method used is the probability stratified random sampling technique. Then, a filtration process was conducted to exclude elderly patients who couldn't read after finishing their consultation with family physicians. The patients were directed to a separate room to meet the researcher to answer the online questionnaire in a secure, confidential environment. The survey started during the second week of March 2022 and continued till the end of April 2022. Based on pre-study considerations of statistical power and the overall number of the elderly population, a minimum sample size of 390 was calculated and considered a confidence level of 95% with a margin of error of 5% to determine the sample size. In addition, to compensate for the design effect, a sample size of more than 600 exceeded the target (Fugard & Potts, 2015).

Table 3.2 Sample size chosen in our research (Author)

		Sampling Technique	Sample Size	Who?	
1	Questionnaire	Random	627	Elderly patients who used telehealth	
2	Interviews	Judgmental for 3 groups:		All participants are used telehealth	
		1. Nursing	8		
		2. Family Physicians	8		20
		3. Elderly patients	4		
		Total	647		

3.8.3 Survey Data Collection

At the end of January 2022, the patients' lists with all details needed in the research were received from the Medical Records Department. Then, the survey google form was created in both languages, and the researcher surveyed in different health centres for seven weeks, from the second two weeks of March till the end of April 2022. In this research study phase, the questionnaire (survey) will be distributed electronically on tablets among elderly patients attending primary healthcare clinics in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

The online survey questionnaire used in this research comprises several closed-ended questions distributed into three sections – demographic questions, quality of life section with five main questions, each question with four choices, and usability and acceptance of telehealth section with seven questions; each number of questions will be rated on a three-point Likert Scale from 1 to 3, where 1 is agreed, 2 to a certain extent and 3 disagree.

627 patients were met to answer the online questionnaire, representing the sample size of elderly patients' responses for research purposes. Descriptive researches usually rely on several advantages in health project; Whitehead (2007) identifies five principal benefits of the survey (1) Surveys present standardized uniform questions for all elderly respondents; (2) Questionnaires' uniformity offers effectiveness in the easiness of administering a survey; (3) A survey can encouragement a researcher dive under the surface by collecting insights on the inspiration and motivations conditions that influence high authorities decisions; (4) The questionnaire's standardization allocates computerized data analysis software to analyse the data gathered efficiently; and (5) Because surveys expand big sample size, they can determine differences between sub-groups. A significant sample size allows the researcher to develop generalizations from the research (Wisdom et al., 2012).

This study uses a self-administered survey to collect data (a copy of the study survey can be found in (Appendix A). The low cost of this method drove the choice of this survey method compared to other methods. Moreover, a self-administered survey offers the research with the anonymity of the respondents, which can significantly contribute to having more honesty and openness in answering the questions. 627 responses were received, 617 to the Arabic version and 10 to the English version, and excluded 27 forms due to errors in elderly writing. The target sample was completed for the study.

3.8.4 Survey Analysis

Elderly patient responses were collected from the participants and imported into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. A self-administrative survey was used in the data collection method in this research. In view of that, the researcher organized the appropriate coding scheme for each variable. The data analysis was performed and achieved at two levels: descriptive and inferential analysis. Figure 3.2. illustrates the data analysis methods used for this research.

Figure 3.5 Data analysis approaches(Ozawa & Pongpirul, 2014)

Descriptive and inferential analysis determines the perception of elderly risky patients on their

QoL after using telehealth in primary health care clinics. Throughout the analysis, differences and relationships are taken by considering different variables and responses. And some elements are correlated with others. analysing the 20 questionnaire questions and computing the variables in terms of mode, mean, median, and standard deviation. Using correlation analysis, Inferential statistics will be conducted to identify the sub-factors that affect elderly telehealth on their QoL. The researcher combined the categorical variables in some questions to 2x2 or 3x3 and correct p-value. This approach is commonly used in a mixed model (Jaeger, 2008).

3.8.5 Survey Analysis Approaches

Elderly Participants' answering from the online questionnaire was imported into SPSS. Consequently, the proper coding for each variable was created. This was followed by assigning and identifying the measurement level (nominal, ordinal, or scale).

✓ Descriptive analysis

In this research, descriptive and inferential analysis were created using the below methods and techniques:

- Frequency tables: using this method, the questionnaire responses are demonstrated in percentages and frequency tables. For example, this was done to distribute respondents by the health centre.
- Graphical representation: using a bar or pie chart to represent the visual display. Which is used to illustrate the respondent's distribution according to the elderly age, educational level, living arrangement, dependency, and the number of telehealth services used by elderly patients.

✓ Inferential analysis

The second level of data analysis is inferential analysis. Which includes:

- Hypotheses testing
 - As the data of the study is not normally distributed, hypotheses be tested using the below nonparametric tests, as the data of the research is not normally distributed:
- Correlation analysis: This test assesses the correlation between the independent variable (used telehealth services) and the dependent variable (QOL dimensions such as mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain or discomfort, anxiety, or depression) using a different test such as:
 - ANOVA Test: Analysis of Variance used to compare the means of continuous variables between more than two independent groups, which are statistically

significant (Jaeger, 2008).

- Chi-Square Test: tell the statistician whether there are significant differences between the expected and observed values in one or more categories. If the values are correlated, there is a relationship between the two categories, and the *p*. value help to identify the presence of correlation only but not the strength.
 - Fisher`s Test: used only when Chi-Square has more than 20% of the expected values in cells
 - Phi and Creamer Test: to assess the correlation strength of the relationship between variables` values (Akoglu, 2018).
- In all statistical tests mentioned above, a *p*-value of less than 0.05 will be statistically considered significant
 - Exploratory Factor analysis

Finally, exploratory factor analysis was used to validate the research framework, as there is no evidence of a framework/model for assessing the impact of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth on their QoL in primary health care (Heale & Twycross, 2015).

3.9 Qualitative Method

A qualitative approach concentrates on the deep understanding of human perception and experiences, how individuals think, and direct access to the individual's content heads, behave and react without struggling to generalize (Leung, 2015). Incorporate qualitative studies with evidence-based best practice experiences and adopt this motivation approach, direct interaction between the researcher and the interviewees promoting instrumental utility and appropriate research tool. Qualitative research finding fills the gap between different elements like understanding and action and between effectiveness, “what work in research,” and effectiveness, “what works in practice” (Sandelowski, 2004, p 1374). Health qualitative research designs systematically influence research decisions associated with sampling, data collection, analysis, and conclusion.

3.9.1 Sampling and data collection

Semi-structured interviews were conducted; the interview comprised a set of 7 open-ended questions on the perception of elderly high-risk patients' using telehealth services on their QoL,

exploring the interviewer about telehealth challenges that affect elderly QoL and their recommendation to improve QoL for older adults. The questions were developed from the conceptual model figure 3.2, designed to be comprehensive to identify the effect of telehealth services on elderly QoL.

In April 2022, the semi-structured interview questions went through pilot testing on a small random sample of health professionals and patients. This research pilot testing was performed with two family physicians with telehealth experience, and interviews were performed with eight nurses, eight health care professionals, and four elderly patients who used telehealth met the selection criteria. Referring to Deterding & Waters (2021), the Strauss and Corbin principle of saturation is used to decide when to stop interviews as the information provided by interviewees begins to converge, and no extra new information emerges.

The pilot provided inputs to validate the question's order, filter, and clear phrasing. The researcher prepared the invitation e-mails providing the date and time of the interview, and background documentation of the research (e.g., objectives, goals, questions), which were sent to 8 health professionals, eight nurses, and four patients. Furthermore, the researcher secures conditions (duration and confidentiality) to allow the interviewees to express their opinion and expectations freely.

Referring to Guest et al. (2020), Glaser and Strauss's principle of saturation determines when to stop interviews as no additional information was obtained. The interview was audio-taped and lasted around 35 minutes with the English language for health professionals and Arabic language with the patients, then translated to English. The interview guide was used (Appendix B) to catch the interview's maximum amount of information.

3.9.2 Data Analysis

MAXQDA software was used to perform and manage the interview transcription. Categorization and coding of the interviewers. The analysis's outcome was visually presented through the software to observe any positive or negative relationships that affect elderly QoL. In addition, the recommendation and suggestions will help to encourage improvement in elderly telehealth impact on their QoL. The three qualitative data records are 1) the interview with family physicians, 2) the interview with the head of the administration office, and 3) the interview with the patients discussing their experience with telehealth in terms of improving QoL, challenges, and

recommendations to improve telehealth that affect their QoL.

The MAXQDA software functions illustrate the main codes of the research and organise the respondents' answers. The following steps were used:

In the first step, all files were imported to the software and categorised accordingly to separate sheets with the audio recording of the interviews. Second, all the codes related to the five dimensions of QoL, challenges, and recommendations were listed, and the sub-categories were added under each dimension related to the concept. Below each main dimension code, the participants' reflections and answers were provided, enabling the researcher to present findings and gather the primary data into logical themes. They could agree/disagree, explain (WHY), and recommend improving the service (HOW). As for the interview with the medical staff, the interview's main objective was to highlight the challenges of the main complaints of the elderly regarding using telehealth and recommendation to improve telehealth which reflects in elderly QoL. The main codes used were: QoL dimensions, challenges, elderly and medical staff complaints, acceptance, usability, and suggestions.

Third, memos and code memos were created with the definitions and information related to the transcription findings. In the fourth step, the coding outcome was presented by visual tools, MAXmaps and MAXstat. The data were organised to conduct and analyse the respondents' answers from the transcription.

3.9.3 Validity of instrument and result

The validity of the research instruments was recognised to measure whether the findings represent what they are meant to represent. This study used qualitative semi-structured interviews, and quantitative structured questionnaires were used to validate the results through the triangulation process. The content validity of the research methodology was assured by presenting them to the academic advisor of the research, who was asked to assess the accuracy of the items of the research instruments and carry out any relevant modification that serves the study. In addition, reviewed by highly qualified researchers in the MoH research committee. The interview questions and questionnaire were pilots tested before the application stage.

3.9.4 Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research

Trustworthiness reflects the degree of confidence in data analysis to ensure the quality of the

study's methods. The researcher took the following measures:

- To achieve the perspectives of experienced medical staff professionals using telehealth and elderly patients' information and telephone numbers from the medical records department were obtained. Health professionals and administration employees were permitted to interview them. In other instances, the researcher used her own laptop, tabs, and network to contact the participants in data collection to certify and ensure the validity of the data interpretation.
- The background, which includes years of experience, and the education level of each medical staff and patient, enhances the depth and richness of the knowledge gathered.
- Credibility Triangulation asks the same research questions of various review members' participants and gathers information from multiple sources through various strategies to respond to similar questions. Member checks happen when analysts request that members survey the data gathered by interviewers and the scientists' understandings of that data (Connelly, 2016).
- Dependability relates more to reliability. The codes were set at two levels (broad and more specific) to drive the themes. The pre-set and developing codes were peer-checked through an expert panel as mentor-reviewed and academic advisor-reviewed to ensure the researcher's accuracy of the researcher's final data analysis (Gunawan, 2015).
- Triangulation decreases the effect of bias by the investigator and provides a more comprehensive and complete image of the research phenomenon.
- Detailed utilisation of the transcription technique and prepared system coding plan using computer program modalities to ensure trustworthiness.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

The survey avoided using inappropriate, discriminatory, or offensive language to formulate survey questions. The author will submit the proposal for approval from the ethics committee in primary health care. Also, it will be conducted utilising main ethical issues, including autonomy, informed consent, confidentiality, privacy, safety, and data protection. Respondents have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose before answering the research questionnaire and conducting the research process with clear objectivity. Moreover, the privacy of individual

information and the confidentiality of given answers were guaranteed. Provide enough time for the completion and submission of the questionnaire with respect to all individuals participating in the research process. Using professional words or ideas were fully recognized through proper citation. Then verbal consent will be taken from both patients & interviewers. They will be informed that their participation is entirely voluntary, there is no obligation to participate, and they have the right to drop out of the survey at any time.

Moreover, it will not impact their care at this health centre if they choose not to participate. The questionnaires will not request participants' names or ID numbers to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Secure passwords will be activated to ensure the security of data on the laptop. Finally, according to the MPM Thesis Development Guidelines Manual, the author follows the APA referencing system and all scientific information extracted from published articles and primary health care websites (Meurman, 2016).

3.11 The outcome of the Literature Review

Based on the selected literature, variables have been selected for analysis.

3.11.1 Variables' definitions

Dependent Variable: include success telehealth session: as the meaning of telehealth “a collection of methods enhancing health care, health education delivery and public health, to support using telecommunications technologies” (Markert, Sasangohar, et al. 2021, p 2). And how to succeed in the telehealth session through acceptance, usability, and having devices and networks to take comprehensive benefits from these services.

Table 3.3 Definitions of Dependent Variables

Individual Dimension	Definition
Using Telehealth Services	The ease of using the technology significantly impacts the users as the perceptions of usefulness and ease of use affect intention and attitude to use telehealth (Pool et al., 2022). Ease of use, “user-friendly” telehealth, and acceptance of the system significantly impact the adoption of elderly telehealth (N. Chen & Liu, 2022)

Independent variables include five European QoL domains (mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain or discomfort, and anxiety or depression).

Table 3.4 Definitions of Independent Variables

QoL Dimension	Definition
Mobility	<p>Evaluate elderly physical activity, including the ability to rise from a chair, walk three meters, turn, walk back, sit down, and move from one place to another. Mobility is not just walking but extends to completing different tasks freely without difficulties, as in Independence in walking (Yu et al., 2021).</p> <p>Getting up from the chair, sitting down, turning while walking, and raising the feet while walking (Kind et al., 2005).</p>
Self-Care	<p>Elderly with an independent self-care profile are more autonomous in their daily life activity, set skills, and abilities related to mobility, motor skills, coordination, balance, and cognitive ability such as feeding, bathing, brushing hair, toileting, and preparation and administration of medicine (Prakash et al., 2021). Which helps promote a high level of autonomy and increases self-esteem and stimulation of cognitive</p>

	function (Elmersjö, 2020).
Usual Activity	Recreational and leisure activities as the elderly engage in hobbies like stamp collection, reading, crossword puzzles, or walking (Cohen et al., 2006). They also include household activities on regular bases, such as helping prepare meals, washing dishes, ironing clothes, and cleaning the home—in addition to social activity and praying (C.-S. Lin et al., 2018).
Pain or Discomfort	Unpleasant sensory and emotional sensations associated with diseases or injury for older adults for more than three months. Pain is also related to gait abnormalities, deconditioning, accidents, cognitive decline, and polypharmacy that lead to elderly suffering. Discomfort means the feeling of uneasiness, annoyance, and distress sensation to physical or mental disturbance like joint stiffness in the morning for elderly patients (Kind et al., 2005).
Anxiety or depression	Depression means loss of elderly self-esteem (powerlessness, helplessness, and alienation), loss of meaningful roles (work productivity), and declining social contacts; with a decrease in mental and health function, the elderly feel unhappy, cheerless, miserable, and sad (Kind et al., 2005). Anxiety means loss of sense of safety and fear of death and health.

Moderating Variables: Depend on each elderly and health care provider situation and may give weight to the other intervening variables. See Table 3.5 below.

Table 3.5 Definitions of Moderating Variables

Individual Dimension	Definition
Age	Gerontologists classify the elderly according to their ages into subgroups, 60-69 years young old, 70-79 years middle old, and 80 and above oldest -old. Young old found to use telehealth more as they are more skilful at using technology due to the aging process

	and decline in cognitive function that alter the use of technology (Dhakal et al., 2020).
Educational level	The participant's education level impacts the acceptance of how to use telehealth, as a highly educated group will learn new technology skills and recognise the use of telehealth to facilitate independence and maintain their health in their own home (N. Chen & Liu, 2022).
Living arrangement	<p>“Co-residential arrangements” is referred to the household structure of old people. When they live with at least one child or another relative, the phrase “coresidence” is used. When the elderly live with no other relative or are unmarried and living with no other kin, the expression “living alone” is used (Zhang et al., 2020).</p> <p>The participant's living situation impacts the well to use telehealth; elderly utilization of telehealth is higher for those living with other partners and family members as they receive technical family support (Chung et al., 2021). On the other hand, living alone without a network is more prone individuals to use telehealth than those who live with family members (N. Chen & Liu, 2022).</p>
Dependency	Elderly with a chronic medical disability enhance individuals to complete a performance task that is accomplished alone previously, which is insufficiency responsible for their wellbeing and health (Timonen & Lolic, 2020). Describe and relate to the perception of dependency when receiving health care services.
Acceptance to technology	The approval, favourable reception, and ongoing use of newly introduced devices and systems” (K. Chen & Chan, 2011)p1, Level of acceptance includes an attitude towards behaviour. The individuals have positive or negative feelings toward the technology.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis & Result

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the main results and findings of the study. It is divided into four main parts; the first part presents the participants' descriptive analysis and baseline characteristics. The second part represents the results of the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth on their QoL questionnaire. The third part compares and examines the correlation between demographic data and questionnaire components (i.e., comparing the first and second parts of the results). The questionnaire part (second part) consists of three parts: The first part covers the socio-demographic data of the respondents. Then, the fourth part of this section presents the results of the qualitative analysis and the semi-structured interviews.

The questionnaire part (second part) consists of three parts: The first part covers the socio-demographic data of the respondents. The second part of the questionnaire covers the dimensions of patients' Quality of Life, including mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain/ discomfort, anxiety, and depression data, while the third part of the questionnaire shows the levels of usability and acceptance of telehealth systems as seen by patients.

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used to test the hypothesis and models, while the Microsoft Excel program was used for descriptive statistical analysis.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis Finding

4.2.1 Demographic Information of the Participants

A total of 600 elderly patients responded to the questionnaire. The personal data gathered from the respondents included gender, age, marital status, educational level, living arrangements, the presence of the elderly in the clinic, number of telehealth used by the patients in the last 12 months, and presence of comorbidities as reported in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Socio-demographic and Baseline Characteristics of the Participants

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
	Ahmed Ali Kanoo	88	14.7
	Dair	140	23.3
Name of Health Centre	Jidhafs	171	28.5
	Isa Town	121	20.2
	Zallaq	80	13.3
Sex	Male	331	55.2
	Female	269	44.8
Age Group	young old	336	56
	middle old	170	28.3
	oldest-old	94	15.7
Marital Status	Single	35	5.8
	Married	352	58.7
	Divorced	116	19.3
	Widow	97	16.2
Living arrangements	living alone	248	41.3
	with the partner only	180	30
	with partner & another carer	172	28.7
Educational level	primary School	270	45
	secondary School	105	17.5
	high School	59	9.8
	collage Degree	129	21.5
	Postgraduate	37	6.2
The presence of the elderly in the clinic	use wheelchair	74	12.3
	walk in	526	87.7
Number of telehealth sessions that used by the patient in the past year	1 – 2	188	31.3
	3 – 4	191	31.9
	5 – 6	221	36.8
Comorbidities	Diabetes	583	97.2
	Hypertension	414	69
	heart disease	158	26.3
	respiratory diseases	54	9
	joint or osteoporosis	128	21.3
	Others	16	2.7

The average age of the participants was 70.318.22 years, as shown in Table 4.1 with more than half (n = 336, 56.0%) aged between 60 and 69 years, approximately 30% aged between 70 and 79 years, 15.7 percent aged above 80 years. While most of the participants were married (n = 352, 58.7%), only 5.8% of them (n = 35) were single. Divorced and widowed participants constituted 19.3% and 16.2% of the participants, respectively.

Regarding the educational level, approximately half of the participants had a primary school level ($n = 270$, 45.0%). Patients with college degrees constituted only 20% of the participants. Up to 88% of the patients presented to the health care facility as walk-in patients, and only 12% presented using a wheelchair. Most patients (41.3%) were living alone (30%, and 28.7% only with a partner and with both the partner and another carer, respectively).

Almost all participants had diabetes mellitus ($n = 583$, 97.2%), and almost 70% of them were hypertensive (69%, $n = 414$). The least prevalent comorbidity was joint or osteoporosis ($n = 128$, 21.3%), followed by respiratory diseases ($n = 54$, 9%).

4.2.2 Effects of Telehealth Services on the QoL for Elderly High-Risk Patients

This part of the questionnaire determined the impact of telehealth on patients' quality of life, including mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain/discomfort, anxiety, and depression. The responses were as follows:

Table 4.2 Effect of Telehealth Services on the QoL for Elderly High-Risk Patients

QoL Dimension	Effect of telehealth in QoL	Count	Percent age
Telehealth effect the patient's mobility	It has no effect on a patient's mobility	99	16.50%
	It is helping the patient move more often	450	75.00%
	It is making the patient move less often	6	1.00%
	Patient unable to move	45	7.50%
Telehealth effect the self-care of the patient	Patient washes & dresses himself/herself. Telehealth has no effect on that	74	12.30%
	Patient unable to wash or dress him/herself, and telehealth has no effect on that	525	87.50%
	It increases the interest of patient in washing/ dressing	1	0.20%
	It decreases the interest of the patient in washing or dressing	0	0.00%
Telehealth effect the usual activity of the patient	The patient does usual activity, and telehealth has no effect on that	121	20.20%
	The patient is unable to do usual activity, and Telehealth has no effect on that	69	11.50%
	It increases patient usual activity	410	68.30%
	It decreases patient usual activity	0	0.00%

Telehealth effect the patient's pain and discomfort	Patient does not suffer from pain/discomfort, and Telehealth has no effect on that	320	53.30%
	Patients suffer from pain or discomfort; however, telehealth has no effect on pain	126	21.00%
	It increases patient pain or discomfort	5	0.80%
	It decreases patient pain or discomfort	149	24.80%
Telehealth effect the patient's anxiety and depression	Patient does not suffer from anxiety/depression. Telehealth has no effect on that	365	60.80%
	Patient suffers from anxiety or depression. Telehealth has no effect on that	24	4.00%
	It increases the patient's anxiety or depression	2	0.30%
	It decreases patient's anxiety or depression	209	34.80%

The impact of telehealth on the dimensions of patients' quality of life is summarised in table 4.2. In general, the negative effects of telehealth among different aspects of patients' QoL were uncommon.

Effect on Mobility

The most affected dimension of QoL in using telehealth was mobility, as up to 75% of the participants found that telehealth was helping them move more often, compared to 1% of them who found that telehealth made them move less often and 8% of them who were unable to move. A total of 16% of the patients determined that telehealth did not affect their mobility.

Figure 4.1 Effect of Telehealth on Mobility of The Patient

Effect on Self Care

The least affected dimension of QoL in using telehealth was self-care was assessed. As illustrated in Figure 4.2, approximately 9 out of 10 participants were unable to wash or dress themselves compared to 1 out of every 10 participants who could. In both cases, telehealth did not affect the self-care of the patients. One participant only reported that telehealth increased the interest in washing and d dressing. Also, none of the people who took part said telehealth made them less interested in washing or getting dressed.

Figure 4.2 Effect of Telehealth on Self-care of The Patients

Effect on usual activity

The effect of telehealth on patients' usual activities was variable, as shown in figure 4.3. More than 20% of the patients ($n = 121$) found that they could do their usual activity, and telehealth had no effect on that. And 10% (69) were unable to do their usual activity, and telehealth had no effect on that. Nonetheless, approximately 70% of them reported increasing patients' usual activity ($n = 410$). In contrast, none of the patients found telehealth decreased their usual activity.

Figure 4.3 Effect of Telehealth on Usual Activities of the Patients

Effect on pain and discomfort

Although around 75% of patients reported that there was no effect of telehealth on their pain and discomfort, whether they were suffering from pain or not (21% and 53.3%), 149 patients (24.8%) reported that telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort. Only 5 patients (0.8%) reported an increase in their pain and discomfort after using telehealth Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 Effect of Telehealth on Pain or Discomfort of the Patients

Effect on Anxiety and depression

The extent and impact of telehealth on patients' anxiety and depression are illustrated in Figure 4.5. 65% of the people who took part said that telehealth had no effect on their anxiety and depression, while 35% said that telehealth made their anxiety and depression go down.

Figure 4.5 Effect of Telehealth on Patients' Anxiety and Depression

4.2.3 Usability and Acceptance of Telehealth System

The participants evaluated 7 statements about the usability and acceptance of telehealth systems and technologies. The majority of patients agreed that telehealth was simple to use (92.0%, $n=552$). Only 8% ($n = 47$) of the participants found that telehealth was not simple to use. When asked if they could see the clinician on telehealth and when attending the clinic, almost 80% agreed, 1% agreed partially, and 19% disagreed.

The participants asked if they thought telehealth consultation visits were the same as in-person consultations. In response, 56% of participants agreed, while 39% disagreed. The next item was about patients' acceptance of telehealth as a way to receive telehealth services. A total of 78% accepted it as a way to receive health care services. In comparison, less than 19% did not. Very similar responses were given when participants were asked about how comfortable they were when they used the system 78% accepted, and 19% did not.

The patients were then asked whether they would use the telehealth services again. The responses revealed that 78% would use them again, and only 14% of the participants would not use them again. Very similar responses were given to the patients when they were asked whether they liked the system (78% agreed and 16% disagreed).

Usability & Acceptance of Telehealth Opinions	Patients'	Count	Percentage	Mean
It was simple to use the telehealth system	Agree	552	<u>92.0%</u>	1.16
	To an extent	1	0.2%	
Using a telehealth system, the Patient can see the clinician as well as if he/she met in person	Disagree	47	7.8%	1.39
	Agree	480	<u>80.0%</u>	
	To an extent	5	0.8%	
	Disagree	115	19.2%	1.82
	Agree	338	<u>56.3%</u>	
	To an extent	31	5.2%	

Patients think the visit provided over the telehealth system are the same as in-person	Disagree	231	<u>38.5%</u>	
Patient accept telehealth as a way to receive health care services	Agree	467	<u>77.8%</u>	
	To an extent	17	2.8%	1.42
	Disagree	116	19.3%	
Patient feel comfortable communicating with the clinician using the telehealth system	Agree	465	<u>77.5%</u>	
	To an extent	19	3.2%	1.42
	Disagree	116	19.3%	
Patient would use the telehealth service again	Agree	471	<u>78.5%</u>	
	To an extent	35	5.8%	1.37
	Disagree	94	15.7%	
Patient like using the system	Agree	465	<u>77.5%</u>	
	To an extent	36	6.0%	1.39
	Disagree	99	16.5%	

Table 4.3 Usability and Acceptance of Telehealth Systems

Most patients generally found that telehealth was simple to use, felt comfortable using it, liked the system, and would use telehealth services again. Also, most older adults found that the telehealth system was the same as getting care in person, so they agreed that telehealth was a good way to get health care.

4.3. Inferential Analysis

4.3.1 Associations Between Demographic Data with Usability and acceptance of Telehealth

Table 4.4 below shows that the two demographics that showed a positive correlation with the acceptance of telehealth were dependency status and educational level.

Usability of Telehealth in Association with Demographic Data	P-Value
---	----------------

Gender	0.737
Age Group	0.332
Marital Status	0.663
Living arrangements	0.224
Telehealth Group	0.942
Educational level	<u>0.040</u>
Dependency	<u>0.006</u>

*Average mean of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

No differences were found between the overall usability and acceptance of telehealth and different characteristics of the demographics, except for dependency status and educational level. In Table 4.4, the mean of all questions about the usability of telehealth was calculated. Considering that the lower the mean, the higher the acceptance of the use of telehealth, patients with lower educational levels and those who presented in wheelchairs had a higher acceptance of telehealth. Obviously, the patients with lower educational levels and those in wheelchairs had a higher acceptance of telehealth use. Dependency, in particular, strongly affected on the patients' acceptance.

The details of educational level and dependency, which had a significant correlation, are presented in detail below:

Table 4.5 Correlation Between Educational Level and Dependency with Usability and Acceptance of Telehealth

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	P-Value
Educational level	Primary School	1.35	270	0.60	0.040
	Secondary School	1.39	105	0.65	

	High School	1.45	59	0.73	
	Collage Degree	1.56	129	0.74	
	Postgraduate	1.54	37	0.71	
Dependency	Use wheelchair	1.23	74	0.44	0.006
	Walk-in	1.45	526	0.68	

As you can see in the table above, there is a strong link between the level of education and the degree of dependence among older people and their ability to use and accept telehealth.

4.3.2 Correlation between Demographic Data and the Effects of Telehealth on Dimensions of patient QoL

Using a Chi-square test, the correlation between demographic data and the effect of telehealth on dimensions of patients' QoL was assessed, as shown in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6 Correlation between Effect of Telehealth QoL and Demographic Data

QoL Dimensions	Special Test	Demographic Data					
		Sex	Age Group	Marital Status	Living arrangement	Educational level	Dependency
To what extent does telehealth affect the mobility of the patient	Chi-Square			0.001**		0.001**	0.001**
	Fisher's exact	0.141	0.001**		0.001**		
	Cramer's V	0.095	0.466	0.230	0.254	0.218	0.779
To what extent does telehealth affect on self-care of the patient	Chi-Square						
	Fisher's exact	0.552	0.675	0.413	0.413	0.454	0.877
	Cramer's V	0.037	0.036	0.049	0.049	0.078	0.015
To what extent does telehealth affect the usual activity of the patient	Chi-Square	0.341	0.001**	0.001**	0.001**	0.001**	0.001**
	Fisher's exact						
	Cramer's V	0.020	0.402	0.321	0.288	0.361	0.507
To What extent does telehealth affect the patient Pain & discomfort	Chi-Square						
	Fisher's exact	0.067	0.084	0.161	0.441	0.003**	0.136
	Cramer's V	0.093	0.086	0.071	0.050	0.145	0.048
To what extent does telehealth affect the patient anxiety or depression	Chi-Square						
	Fisher's exact	0.001**	0.001**	0.001**	0.001**	0.034*	0.007**
	Cramer's V	0.139	0.137	0.246	0.346	0.111	0.131

* Significant at 0.05

**Significant at 0.01

The tested correlations between QoL and demographic data are sorted according to their strengths in Table 4.7 below (Akoglu, 2018):

Correlation Strength	Cramer's	Effect of QoL with Demographic data
Strong Correlation (Greater or equal to 0.5)	.0779	Effect of mobility with dependency
	0.507	Effect of usual activity and dependency
Moderate Correlation (0.3-0.5)	.466	Effect of mobility with age group
	.402	Effect of usual activity with age group
	.322	Effect of usual activity with marital status
	.361	Effect of usual activity with educational level
	.346	Effect of anxiety and depression with living arrangement
Low Correlation (0.1-0.3)	.254	Effect of mobility with living arrangement
	.218	Effect of mobility with educational level
	.176	Effect of mobility with marital status
	.288	Effect of usual activity with living arrangement
	.205	Effect of pain and discomfort with educational level
	.139	Effect of anxiety and depression with gender
	.137	Effect of anxiety and depression with age group
	.256	Effect of anxiety and depression with marital status
	.111	Effect of anxiety and depression with educational level
.131	Effect of anxiety and depression with dependency	

* >.5 high association

0.3 to 0.5 moderate association

0.1 to 0.3 low association

0 to 0.1 no association

As presented in the table, the tested correlations between demographics and effects of telehealth on dimensions of patients' QoL were significant except for the impact of telehealth on self-care and pain or discomfort. Gender had no effect on the dimensions of QoL except on anxiety and depression.

In general, there is a relationship between using telehealth services and improving the quality of life in some dimensions with demographic factors. For example, telehealth services improved mobility with age group, marital status, living arrangement, educational level, and

dependency as well as usual activity, and decreased anxiety or depression in the elderly's quality of life in relation to all demographic data. At the same time, telehealth services had no effect on the self-care dimension of the elderly's quality of life and no effect on the pain or discomfort dimension of the elderly's quality of life, though 25% of the participants reported a good effect (telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort). In appendix C, you will find SPSS chi-Sequence, Fisher Exact Test, and Cremer. The details of the correlation tested are as follows

4.3.3 Correlation between Demographic data no 1: QoL with gender

The gender of the user of telehealth services influenced the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly anxiety and depression significantly (Fisher Exact Test p 0.001). It was found that telehealth decreased anxiety and depression among males by 40.8% in comparison to females by 27.5%. However, gender reported no impact on other dimensions of QoL.

4.3.4 Correlation with Demographic data no2: QoL and Age

The age of the user of telehealth services influenced the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, anxiety, and depression significantly, as shown in Table 4.6 (p 0.001). The majority of young and middle-aged patients (83.9%) and less than a third of the elderly (31.9%) found it to reduce anxiety and depression (Fisher Exact Test p 0.001). Similarly, by testing the correlation between age and usual activity (p 0.001), the result showed that telehealth increased the usual activity of young and middle-aged patients (78.6% and 71.8%, respectively), but not that of the oldest-old patients (25.5%). However, 74.3% of all age groups reported no impact of telehealth on pain and discomfort. Nonetheless, only 21% of young-old, 30.6% of middle-aged, and 26.6% of the oldest-old patients reported that telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort, with no significant correlation between the two. Additionally, a positive impact of telehealth on patients' mood was specifically observed among the oldest-old group, with 55.3% of them stating that telehealth decreased their depression (Fisher exact test p 0.001). In contrast, two-thirds of the young and middle-aged groups reported no impact of telehealth on their anxiety and depression status.

4.3.5 Correlation with Demographic data no3: QoL and Educational Level

The educational level of the user of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility and usual activity ($p < 0.001$) of the Chi-square test. Anxiety or depression ($p < 0.001$) using the Fisher Exact Test. This association is illustrated in table 4.6 and appendix C. Regardless of the educational level, most patients reported that telehealth improved their mobility by 75% and increased their usual activities by 68.3%; the findings were more evidenced among highly educated patients by 92.7% and 91%, respectively. In addition to decreasing pain and discomfort, it found a significant correlation between the two (Fisher exact test $p < 0.001$) among all levels of education by 25%. The impact of telehealth on decreasing patients' anxiety and depression by 35% was also observed between all levels of education.

4.3.6 Correlation with Demographic data no 4: QoL and living arrangement

According to table 4.6 and appendix C, the living arrangement of the user of telehealth services significantly influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, anxiety, and depression ($p < 0.001$) by using the Fisher exact test. Using the Chi-square test, living arrangements significantly influence the relationship between using telehealth and usual elderly activity. More than 50% of those who lived alone reported that telehealth decreased their anxiety and depression, compared to around 20% of those who lived with other people. Additionally, patients who lived alone also noted that the telehealth helped them move more often compared to those who lived with a partner alone and those who lived with a partner and other caregivers (87.5%, 75.6%, and 56.4%, respectively).

The impact of telehealth use on decreasing pain and discomfort was seen among those who lived alone or with a partner only (26.6% and 28.3%, vs. 18.6% in those who lived with a partner and other caregivers). However, regardless of the living arrangement, most patients (70-80%) reported that telehealth had no impact on their pain and discomfort. Likewise, all patients reported that telehealth had no effect on their self-care, though variations existed, as presented in the appendix C.

4.3.7 Correlation with Demographic data no 5: QoL and Dependency

The dependency of the user on telehealth services influences the significant positive relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity through the Chi-square test ($P < 0.001$), anxiety, or depression which testing with Fisher exact test ($P < 0.001$). While most

patients who presented in a wheelchair were unable to move, telehealth did not affect their self-care, usual activities, pain, and discomfort; 51% of them reported that telehealth decreased their anxiety and depression. In contrast, 33% of those who presented as walk-ins reported that telehealth decreased their depression and anxiety. Around 80% thought that telehealth increased their usual activities and helped them move more often. Still, it did not affect their self-care (99.8%).

4.3.8 Correlation with Demographic data no 6: QoL and Marital status

The survey results indicate that the marital status of the users of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, anxiety, and depression by using Chi-square and Fisher exact test ($P < 0.001$), as illustrated in Table 4.6. Most elderly found that they move more with telehealth; they are single approximately 97.1% and divorced 94.8%. In this regard, the survey results demonstrated an increase in usual activity of the elderly who used telehealth among single and divorced by 91.4%, 93.1% respectively. The similarity of the effect found in decreasing anxiety and depression is a large proportion of participants are divorced and widows with 55.2% and 56.7%. On the other hand, telehealth has no effect on all marital statuses with self-care, pain, and discomfort, as seen in the previous table.

The survey result demonstrated that some demographic data did not affect elderly QoL, even though descriptive analysis reported a significant impact on selected demographic on elderly QoL; for example, there is a strong correlation between mobility and usual activity with dependency. For example, moderate correlation between usual activity with age group, marital status, and educational level. On the contrary, many significant demographic factors have a weak correlation with dimensions of QoL, as shown in Table 4.6

4.3.9 Correlation between QoL dimensions with Usability and Acceptance of Telehealth

4.3.9.1 Using the ANOVA test, the correlation between QoL dimensions with acceptance of telehealth is assessed in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8 QoL dimensions and acceptance of telehealth

QoL	ANOVA P-value
Mobility of the Patient	0.040*
Self-Care of the Patient	0.487
usual activity of the patient	0.658
Patient Pain and Discomfort	0.596
Patient Anxiety or Depression	0.100

* Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Merge was used for (2,3,4,5) from part C (Appendix C)

The impact of telehealth on patients' QOL dimensions was compared with the acceptance of telehealth as viewed by patients. The effect of telehealth on patients' mobility was a significant predictor of its acceptance using the (Anova- test p -value <0.040). While there is no correlation between acceptance and the other four dimensions.

4.3.9.2 Correlation between QoL dimensions with Usability of Telehealth using an average of ANOVA Test

Table 4.9 Usability of Telehealth System with QoL

QoL	ANOVA P-value*²
Mobility of the Patient	0.001**
Self-Care of the Patient	0.519

² ANOVA test (merge usability Questions in part C) Q1,6 and 7

usual activity of the patient	0.001**
Patient Pain and Discomfort	0.085
Patient Anxiety or Depression	0.001**

** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The effect of telehealth system usability on QoL dimensions showed a significant correlation (Anova Test p -value <0.001) with mobility, usual activity, anxiety, or depression, but not with self-care or pain or discomfort

4.3.10 Summary of the Chapter

In general, there is a relationship between using telehealth services and elderly quality of life in some dimensions. For example, using telehealth services improved mobility, increased the usual activity dimension, and decreased the anxiety or depression in the elderly's quality of life. At the same time, telehealth services had no effects on the self-care and pain or discomfort dimension in the elderly's quality of life, as 25% of the participants reported a good effect (telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort).

Usability of telehealth increase with the elderly, who stated that telehealth increases their mobility and usual activity and decreases their anxiety and depression, as illustrated in Table 4.9.

4.4 Qualitative Findings

This chapter presents the results of the study. The first section will present the data collected from the semi-directive interviews, which will be synthesised and summarized into various themes accordingly. MAXQDA software was used to facilitate the transcription of the interview and the answers to the questions by managing and organizing the outcomes and the results by themes. The qualitative data will be used to validate the result of the survey and enhance the impact of the discussion. Most importantly, it will achieve the research objective and answer sub-research questions. In the last part of this chapter, a summary of what was found will be given.

4.4.1 Interview Data Analysis

4.4.1.1 Profile of the Participants

A total of 20 interviews were conducted with the participant who signed up for the study and agreed to participate. Eight of the twenty interviews were conducted with physicians, eight with nurses, and four with patients. Seven physicians were Family Physicians, seven nurses held a BSc degree, two patients were female, and two were male. The sample size was sufficient to reach data saturation.

Patients	0
How do you feel when you use telehealth at home?	4
How does using telehealth services make you feel independent a	4
How does telehealth help you to become socially interactive?	4
How do you describe the health care provider's attitude and be	4
Can you describe any problems or difficulties you had when you	4
What are the improvements you recommend to the services?	4
How did you use telehealth services to better reduce your pain	4
Nurses	0
How do you perceive the use of TS by the patients?	8
How do you help the patients? What type of services do you prov	8
How do judge the effectiveness of the TS? Is it effective with	8
Do you think that the use of TS improve the QoL of the patients	8
Based on your experience how we can improve the effectiveness o	8
Doctors	0
How do you think that telehealth services reflected on patients	8
How do you compare the trust relationship between you and your	8
Can you describe any problems or difficulties you had when you	8
What are the improvements you recommend to the services?	8
How are your patients making use of telehealth services to redu	8
How does telehealth reflects on patients mobility and social ac	8
Which devices are often used (mobile phone, PC, or iPad)? and h	8

Figure 4.6 structural coding

Coded the documents with the structural codes and performed a content analysis of the data. The interviews were coded independently, line by line, allowing new codes to emerge inductively using MAXQDA (Version 2020). Categories and subcategories were continually revised in a cyclical process, with new categories created to reflect the reality of research data.

Figure 4.7 Word cloud of the top 50 word

Figure 4.8 Interactive word tree for the term telehealth

Studying the word cloud of the high-frequency words and interactive word tree helps to get the visual display of the text data. It looks at word combinations in contexts and gets an idea of the transcripts.

Seven overarching themes characterized the effects of telehealth services on the quality of life for elderly high-risk patients: decreasing anxiety and depression, assisting high-risk patients in their self-care, assisting them in their usual routine, availability of the network and devices for telehealth, reducing pain and discomfort, and assisting them in their mobility. Even though telehealth made things easier and got more health professionals involved, participants were worried about the different problems they faced, the clinical effectiveness and limits of virtual physical exams, and the possibility that access differences could get worse. Many people gave suggestions on how to improve the quality of life (QoL) of older people who used telehealth and were at high risk.

Figure 4.9 Code map showing the Perception of Elderly High-Risk Patients of Using Telehealth Services on Their QoL

4.4.1.2 Objective of Research

Table 4.10 represents Themes and their frequency in the documents

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Theme 5: Decreasing pain or discomfort for elderly patients	19
Theme 4: Assisting the elderly patients in their usual activity	18
Theme 1: Ease of use and trust	17
Theme 2: Decrease in anxiety or depression for elderly patients	15
Theme 6: Helps in the mobility	11
Theme 7: availability of the network and devices	10
Theme 3: Helpful in self-care of elderly patients	9

The previous Table represents the number of documents assigned to each theme (codes and subcodes). All the codes in a given document were counted on a per-document basis. It represents the themes. For example, “decreasing pain or discomfort in the elderly patients” is the most frequently assigned code, and the theme “helpful in the self-care of elderly patients” is the least frequently assigned code in all the documents.

Theme 1: Ease of use and trust

Table 4.11 represents the sub-theme of ease of use and trust

When	Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency	asked the
	The same level of trust	13	
	Easy for patients with chronic diseases	9	
	comfortable environment and relax at home	8	

participants to compare the trust relationship between using telehealth or attending the clinic, 13

of the respondents mentioned that level of trust was the same in both telehealth and presenting to the clinic. Nine participants revealed that telehealth is easy to use for elderly patients. Eight participants noted a comfortable environment would be provided as the elderly would relax at home: *“I think doctor-patient rapport largely depends on how the doctor conducts himself, whether in the clinic or through the phone or video, how professionals use verbal and nonverbal clues such as body language, eye contact, voice tone, and empathy and the physician can build the same level of trust in both clinic and telehealth.”*; *“I don’t think that my trust relationship will be affected during telehealth as long as this patient is already seen me before during face-to-face consultation, so both are trustful relationship.”*

Theme 2: Decreases anxiety and depression in patients

Table 4.12 represents the sub-theme of Decreasing anxiety and depression in patients

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Provide privacy to the patients	8
Can talk freely to physician	7
Accessibility of health services	7
A comfortable environment relieves stress	5
Physical appointments cause anxiety for the patients	5
Consultation for sensitive issues	4
Provide advice to deal with anxiety	3

Regarding anxiety and depression QoL, eight respondents mentioned that telehealth provides privacy to the patients: *“as elderly came with the caregiver so no privacy at the consultation”*; *“there is security environment in telehealth as physician ensure patients identity before the consultation.”* Seven participants added that telehealth offers a channel for the elderly to talk freely to their physician as some are shy to speak in a face-to-face consultation: *“It is provided a way*

for people who were afraid of mental health stigma to attend clinics so they can be counseled in a comfortable private home.”; “I feel shy to explore my stress and anxiety during face to face consultation.” Four participants added that the elderly could consult their physician for sensitive issues: “my slipper full down while walking as my sensation decrease in my feet”; “I can talk freely about my sexuality affected with diabetes.” Seven interviewees noted that telehealth decreases stress by facilitating access to health services. Moreover, five participants noted that telehealth provides a comfortable environment to relieve stress. Another five participants mentioned that physical appointments could accelerate anxiety and depression: “When I attend the clinic, I became very stressful, and my blood pressure shot up (white coat hypertension), so through telehealth, I can contact physicians and feel comfortable when we call them.” Finally, three participants suggested providing the elderly with medical advice to decrease their anxiety “the doctor in telehealth provide me with educational video for exercise that I can practice at home and reduce mt stress.”

Theme 3: Helpful in the self-care of elderly patients

Table 4.13 represents the sub-theme of Helpful in the self-care of elderly patients

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Diet advise and control	13
Keep them safe from infectious diseases	4
Educating the elderly about healthier lifestyles	4
Providing advice for hygiene	2

Concerning helping elderly patients in self-care, thirteen participants indicated the importance of giving patients diet advice and control, and four participants noted that telehealth help to keep the elderly in a safe environment away from infectious diseases. Four participants suggested

educating the elderly about healthier lifestyles to help them to improve their self-care. Lastly, two participants mentioned that we should give the elderly advice on hygiene that will benefit them.

Theme 4: Assisting the elderly patient in their usual activity

Table 4.14 represents the sub-theme of Assisting the elderly patient in their usual activity

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Educating patients to do exercise	14
Regular intake of medications	9
Help in social activities	7
Appointment scheduling	2

The interviews showed that fourteen participants indicated how important it is to educate the elderly about how exercising will help them in their usual activities: *“my doctor advised me to exercise and walk”*; *“I can open the link to exercise while cleaning, washing dishes, and doing relaxation exercises while watching TV.”* Nine other respondents mentioned that adhering to regular medication will decrease disease complications and enhance activity: *“daily exercise, such as stretching while reading books, helps relieve the joint pain and reduce the consumption of analgesia medication like voltrain and helps to move better.”*. Seven participants mentioned receiving a special support scheme to motivate the elderly to engage in social activities: *“my physician suggested I walk for 20 minutes daily with a friend”*; *“the doctor advised me to participate actively in community activities like going to the mosque and sports and social clubs.”* Two respondents indicated that easy appointment scheduling would help older people increase their dependency and empower them: *“I can open zoom room alone and talk with my physician and send to him my vital sign reading without any help any time and everywhere.”*

Theme 5: Decreasing pain or discomfort in elderly patients

Table 4.15 represents the sub-theme of Assisting the elderly patient in their usual activity

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Telemedicine	12
helpful as an early detection tool	6
Advice to comfort pain and exercise	6
helpful for the elderly with limited or painful mobility	5
Virtual group classes for physiotherapy	4

Regarding pain reduction and discomfort for elderly users of telehealth services, the interview result showed that twelve respondents said that telemedicine motivates the elderly to adhere to medication and decrease their suffering from pain: *“reviewing elderly medication, doses, frequency, drug-drug interaction, and herbal medication have to impact in decrease elderly pain.”* While six participants suggested that telehealth detect diseases in the early stages that prevent complications and reduce pain: *“the doctor through telehealth discovered my high blood sugar and started me on insulin; I feel much better as the pain in my hands and feet become less.”* In addition, six participants mentioned the importance of giving the elderly advice to comfort pain, and exercise would benefit them: *“Providing me advice on exercise and mobility such as back and neck hygiene. Increase my compliance to medication which helps me to decrease pain and enhance the mobility.”* Four participants indicated that virtual group exercise encourages the elderly to participate in such classes for physiotherapy will reduce their pain: *“team exercise with other patients with similar conditions motivate patients to participate and improve their pain.”* Finally, five participants suggested telehealth will benefit the elderly with joint diseases and disabilities by

providing them with a hospital at home and decreasing their suffering.

Theme 6: Helps in the mobility

Table 4.16 represents the sub-theme of Assisting the elderly patient in their mobility

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Physiotherapy advice improves their mobility	15
Upload applications that increase elderly confidence and autonomy	7
Telemonitoring helps reduce the no of the visit to clinics	5

When asked the interviewees how telehealth reflects on patients' mobility, fifteen of the participants mentioned education to do exercise will help elderly mobility, and seven participants indicated that regular medicine intake would decrease the complication of chronic diseases and motivate the elderly to move: *“advice patients to take medicine regularly as hyperglycemic drugs decrease the risk of fluctuating in blood sugar level, decrease the risk of fall and enhance their mobility.”* Five participants indicated that engaging the elderly in social activities will empower their confidence to move more.

Theme 7: Availability of the network and devices

Table 4.17 represents the subtheme of network & device

Represent Statement of Interview	Frequency
Smart Phone	6
PC	1
Smart Phone, PC & I. Pad	1
Internet speed decrease in hospital and differ from one telecommunication company to another	2

Regarding the availability of devices and internet networks, six participants indicated that smartphones have easy access to telehealth and are preferred by the elderly as simple to use. One

respondent mentioned that PC is more advantageous as it may allow for side-by-side note documentation and making medical patient requests: “I think PC is the best and most efficient.” Some workplaces also have their interfaces loaded on tablets, which can be helpful in the work-from-home setting. Another participant said that smartphones, PC, and I. Pad could be used in telehealth communication. Two participants noted that internet speed decrease in hospitals, and the speed of the internet differs from one telecommunication company to another.

4.4.1.3 Challenges & Recommendations

Tables 4.18 & 4.19 summarise the interview result; the two tables prioritised the result from the most mentioned to the least mentioned challenges and suggested recommendations.

Table 4.18 challenges of interviewee result

Challenges	Frequency
Physical impairment of the elderly with difficulty in physical examination	8
Difficult to find telephone numbers	3
Acceptance of digital technology	2
Language barriers	2
Lack of communication	2
Technical instability	4
Missed call	4

On reviewing challenges, and as eight participants revealed, the most concerning is when the elderly patients have physical impairments like hearing or visual loss, which can make it difficult for them to use technology, follow instructions, conduct a physical examination, and may hinder the benefits of telehealth.

Four participants were concerned about technical instability. Four interviewees also mentioned that unanswered calls interfere with successful telehealth consultation. Moreover, three participants said incorrect telephone numbers were registered in the electronic medical file: “*I spent a long time searching for the correct phone number of the patient.*” Two respondents cited

other constraints regarding the acceptance of technology, language barriers, and lack of communication.

Table 4.19 recommendation suggested by the interviewer

Recommendation	Frequency
24 hours emergency telehealth	6
Multidisciplinary clinic	4
Educational video training courses	3
Mobile home clinic	3
Reminding patients about their telehealth appointment	3
Artificial Intelligent	2
Updating telephone number	1

Regarding telehealth perception of the elderly using telehealth services in their QoL recommendations, six participants indicated the importance of the availability of 24 hours telehealth for emergency cases, and four noted the need for a multidisciplinary clinic: “I think it mandatory to adopt different telehealth specialties to gain more benefit for patients .” Three interviewees suggested educational video training courses, the presence of the mobile home clinic, and reminding the patients about their telehealth appointments: “I need a massage to remind me on my phone about my telehealth appointment.”

In this regard, two participants elaborated on having more advanced applications and artificial intelligence, and one participant suggested the need to update telephone numbers for elderly patients.

4.4.2 Summary of Qualitative Analysis

The qualitative analysis results confirm telehealth's impact on the different dimensions of QoL. The most cited dimensions interviewees thought to improve elderly QoL were pain or discomfort, usual activity, and anxiety and depression. The dimensions that were cited less were mobility and the elderly's self-care.

The results also showed different challenges and recommendations mentioned by the participants, which can help to improve the telehealth system in primary health care.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the findings to answer the research questions and fulfill the study's objectives to explore the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their quality of life. The following section will discuss descriptive, inferential, quantitative, and qualitative analysis findings by discussing the opinion on the effect of using telehealth on elderly quality of life. The third section will answer the research question on elderly acceptance of how to use telehealth and the availability of networks and devices. The fourth section will discuss the main challenges facing elderly patients and medical staff recommendations. The last sections discuss managerial recommendations, research limitations, and future research directions.

5.2 Effect of using telehealth services on the QoL of Elderly High-Risk patients

This section aims to summarise the descriptive and inferential statistics of Euro QoL and usability and acceptance of the online survey, which will answer the first question of the research: What is the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their QoL in Bahrain's primary health care. In Addition to the first eight sub-research questions.

It will also fulfill the research objective; to explore the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their quality of life. The descriptive analysis consisted of 36 questions, which provided insights regarding the patients' characteristics. Descriptive statistics revealed that about 55.2% of the respondents were male. The participants' ages varied from 60 to 80 years and above, and the majority were between 60 and 69 years. Most of them were educated to the primary school level. Most participants were married, 58.7%, and attended health care facilities walk-in 87.7%. Six hundred and forty-seven were Bahraini nationals, and all of them were Arab speaking. In general, with comorbidities of the elderly most participants had diabetes mellitus 97.2%, hypertension 69%, joint or osteoporosis 21.3%, followed by respiratory diseases9%. In addition, the qualitative analysis consists of 20 interviews.

In the core analysis of the five dimensions of Euro QoL, the results, and the tested hypotheses, are discussed accordingly.

5.2.1 Effect of Using Telehealth on Elderly QoL

5.2.1.1 Effect of Using Telehealth on the patient mobility

It was hypothesized that telehealth use has a significant relationship between the usability of telehealth services and the mobility dimension in the quality of life (H1). The results supported this hypothesis with a significant confidence level of $p < 0.001$ of the Anova test. Several studies have shown a significant between the usability of telehealth and mobility QoL of elderly patients (N. Chen & Liu, 2022; Valdivieso et al., 2018; Giordano et al., 2016).

The first question in QoL dimensions related to the effect of telehealth on patient mobility. For instance, 75% of elderly patients reported that telehealth helped them move more, 16.5% reported no effect on mobility, while 7.5% were unable to move. On the other hand, only 1% of telehealth made them move less. Eleven interviewees answered that telehealth improves elderly mobility through the physiotherapy advice of doing exercise, relaxation, and walking, uploaded application that increases patients' confidence and autonomy for mobility and decreases the risk of injury. In addition to telemonitoring vital signs, feel the patient's empowerment to move more. A similar finding was reported by Giordano et al. (2016), who used telehealth for fall prevention programs resulting in improved elderly gait, balance and decreased risk of falls which enhanced patients' mobility.

Telehealth improves the mobility dimension in QoL, as reported in a United Kingdom study by Watson et al. (2021), address that a large proportion of elderly who use telehealth allows them to remain independent in their life with intrinsic value to take their decision to do walking and normal activity and can feel better about their wellbeing and health. (Giordano et al., 2016).

A high respondent rate in the quantitative survey revealed that mobility is one of the telehealth's most significant positive impacts on elderly QoL. In a study reported by Gokalp et al. (2018) and Gokalp & Clarke (2013), the mobility dimension; was positively correlated with telehealth services used by elderly patients.

5.2.1.2 Effect of Using Telehealth on the Patient Self Care

Self-care is one of the components of Europ QoL dimensions (EuroQol Group, 1990). The results

of both the survey and interviews revealed the effect of using telehealth on self-care has no effect as respondents answered with a large proportion that telehealth does not affect self-care. Approximately 99.8% (Anova p value >0.005), comparatively 9 of patients and medical staff conveyed that using telehealth affected elderly self-care.

The results differ from the literature review, reflecting Bahrain's cultural issues and changes in non-communicable diseases for the elderly population. It can be explained as aging with chronic comorbidities causing vitamin deficiencies such as vitamins D and B12 that cause numbness in their periphery. In addition to the experience of chronic diseases, related complications decrease elderly sensation (peripheral neuropathy) that harm the elderly to have burns or injury (Buse et al., 2020). This research did not support this hypothesis, as telehealth services do not affect the self-care dimension in elderly QoL(H3). Several studies have shown a strong relationship between the usability of telehealth and self-care (Tonapa et al., 2021; Kim & Lee, 2019; Valdivieso et al., 2018).

In future telehealth, to improve elderly self-care, adopt self-care counseling and program to recognize factors that may affect elderly self-care with statistical analysis methods such as Self-Care Behavior Scale, Geriatric Depression Scale Short Form, and Self Efficacy Scale. Families with social and health support help to develop stress management strategies, education, and lifestyle modification(Kim & Lee, 2019).

5.2.1.3 Effect of Using Telehealth on the Usual Patient Activity

The result of the hypothesis testing showed a significant relationship between using telehealth services and the usual activity dimension in the quality of life (H4) using (Anova p value <0.005). Kwak et al. (2021) observed a relationship between the usability of telehealth with the elderly usual activity. Finding a significant relationship between the two in terms of sharing experiences of medical illness, medication doses, and side effects with other family members, friends, and patients discussing group and motivating them in social activity participation enhance their empowerment to do their usual home activities.

The result of telehealth's effect on usual activity revealed that 68.3% increased their activity, and 20.2% could do their usual activity, and telehealth has no impact on that. The least present to those who are unable to do the usual activity, and telehealth has no effect 11.5%. In

addition to the qualitative interview, 18 respondents answered that telehealth improves usual activity by educating the elderly to do exercise, regular medication intake, engagement in social activity, and scheduling appointment time that fits with patients. Lang et al. (2021) and Beer et al. (2021) have similar finding that telehealth add value and support the elderly with a wide range of social activities.

Persson et al. (2020) conducted a study on the impact of telehealth on elderly patients by significantly improving elderly usual activity with telehealth. As well as Yu et al. (2021) highlighted the study of assessing elderly user preferences with telehealth solutions showed a strong significant correlation between the use of telehealth with the usual activity, supporting the results of this research.

5.2.1.4 Effect of Using Telehealth on the Patient Pain or Discomfort

As hypothesized, the expected significant correlation between usability of telehealth services and the effect on the elderly pain and discomfort in patients QoL(H5); many researchers have highlighted the positive effect of telehealth and patient's pain and discomfort (Markert, Sasangohar, et al., 2021; Valdivieso et al., 2018). This research does not support this hypothesis, and the relationship between the two was an insignificant correlation.

During the interview, 19 respondents answered that telehealth improves elderly pain and discomfort. The qualitative results are in line with the literature review, which meets the respondent's opinion with literature review as telehealth is used as an early detection tool to discover elderly diseases in the early stages, advice to do exercise through virtual group classes of physiotherapy that limited painful elderly mobility (Beer et al., 2021). In addition to telemedicine, that enhances elderly adherence to their medication, decreases chronic disease complications, and discusses the use of medication to relieve pain and discomfort (Platts-Mills et al., 2020). The expected results from Jensen et al. (2019) were high, significantly meeting the qualitative outcome.

Unfortunately, in a quantitative study, telehealth is not correlated with pain or discomfort (Anova p value > 0.005). 75% of patients reported no effect of telehealth on their pain and discomfort, whether they were suffering from pain or not, and 25% of respondents answered that telehealth decreased pain and discomfort. (0.8%) reported increased pain and discomfort after using telehealth, so the survey result did not support this hypothesis. This indicates that patients

are suffering as most of them have diabetes mellitus that is associated with peripheral nerve inflammation that leads to painful diabetic neuropathy (Giovannini et al., 2021). In addition to multiple medications with comorbidities for elderly patients that interact with drugs for persistent pain, which cause a severe adverse outcome. Another explanation is that osteoporotic patients suffer joint pain and discomfort (Graham & Jones, 2020; Jensen et al., 2019).

5.2.1.5 Effect of Using Telehealth on the Patient Anxiety or Depression

It was hypothesized that the usability of telehealth significantly influences patient anxiety and depression(H6); the data result has expected to link with the (Anova p -value <0.005) and qualitative interview as 15 of the respondents mentioned that telehealth improves patients' anxiety and depression as they mentioned that telehealth provides a comfortable environment. Patients can talk freely about sensitive issues, in addition to giving patients privacy and advice to deal with anxiety. The result of this study is in line with Kwak et al. (2021), Lang et al. (2021), Watson et al. (2021), and Kaveh et al. (2021), as they stated a positive correlation between telehealth and patient anxiety or depression, which supports the results of this research.

In Spain, a study conducted by Valdivieso et al. (2018) “about the effect of telehealth, telephone support or usual care on QoL, mortality and healthcare utilization in elderly high-risk patients with multiple chronic conditions.” showed a strong significant relationship between the expected effect of telehealth and patient anxiety or depression, which supports the results of this research.

Statistics revealed that 65% of the usability of elderly patients to telehealth has no effect on the patient's anxiety or depression, 35% reported a decrease in anxiety, and 0.3% of the respondents stated its increases patients' anxiety and depression. This indicates that, to some extent, telehealth improves the mental status of elderly patients, as interactive social support through interactive corporate programs and group support and discussion with other patients reduce the risk of loneliness and suicidal thoughts (Raja et al., 2021).

5.2.2 Correlation between Demographic Data and QoL:

5.2.2.1 Sex with QoL

The gender of the user of telehealth services influenced the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly anxiety and depression significantly (Fisher Exact Test $p < 0.001$), illustrated in Table 4.6. Telehealth decreased anxiety and depression among males by 40.8% compared to females by 27.5%; N. Chen et al. (2021) suggest that male users are higher than female users of telehealth, as females are willing to use traditional methods during medical consultation compared to males who prefer technology. Another study by Kruse et al. (2020) highlights that computer technology accelerates anxiety among females compared to males as it is too complex and requires skills.

However, the sex of elderly patients noticed no impact on other dimensions of QoL, which is in line with another study (Snowbell et al., 2021).

5.2.2.2 Age with QoL

The age of telehealth users was hypothesized to significantly influence QoL and elderly mobility, usual activity, anxiety, or depression (H7-H9-H11). The results supported this hypothesis with a significant $p < 0.001$ in the special statistical test shown in Table 4.6. There is a moderate positive correlation between the age of the elderly and mobility, usual activity, and weak positive correlation with anxiety or depression of elderly QoL, as illustrated in Table 4.7. When identifying categories of elderly age, it was found in statistical data that young-old 63%, middle -old 30.6% move more compared to oldest-old 6.6%. The survey results similarly supported (N. Chen & Liu, 2022). The research result is supported by ageing characterized by changes in physiological health parameters that affect muscle power and bone density (motor milestone and cognitive ability) that reflect on elderly mobility and unable to perform the usual activity (Ferrucci et al., 2016).

Correspondingly, Telehealth increased the usual activity of young and middle-old patients (64.3% and 29.7%) compared to oldest-old patients (5.8%). The positive impact of telehealth on patients' mood was mainly reported among the oldest-old group (55.3%) study conducted by Darrat et al. (2021); age-related motivational factors rather than complexity in accessing telehealth as the elderly received training to use technology will be more motivated and willing to use the advanced technology. In contrast, two-thirds of the young and middle-old groups reported no impact of telehealth on their anxiety and depression status, which is in line with the statistical result

as older people with long-standing chronic diseases could lead to a decline in physical and mental function (Lang et al., 2021; Kaveh et al., 2021).

5.2.2.3 Educational Level with QoL

The educational level of the user of a telehealth service influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, pain or discomfort, anxiety, or depression ($P < 0.001$) by using Chi-Square or Fisher's Exact Test, as presented in Table 4.6. The result of the hypothesis testing supported and showed a significant relationship between educational level and elderly mobility, usual activity, pain, discomfort, anxiety, or depression (H12-H14-H15 -H16). Data observed reported that telehealth improved their mobility by 75% and increased their usual activities by 68.3%. The latter findings were more evidenced among highly educated patients. The impact of telehealth on decreasing patients' anxiety and depression as statistics revealed 35% and reduced pain and discomfort by 25% was noticed among all levels of education.

In this regard, the survey results denoted a close correlation between education level and some dimensions of elderly QoL in concurrence with the study's outcome (Yu et al., 2021; Marten et al., 2021; Valdivieso et al., 2018). The result also can be explained that most educational elderly can deal efficiently with technology that reflects an improvement of their QoL (N. Chen & Liu, 2022).

5.2.2.4 Marital Status with QoL

The survey results indicate that the marital status of the users of telehealth services positively influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or depression by using either (Chi-square or Fisher Exact Test $p < 0.001$), as illustrated in Table 4.6. Most single and divorced elderly conveyed them to move more (approximately 97.1% and 94.8%) and do usual activities (91.4% and 93.1%). Respectively.

The effect of telehealth found in decreasing anxiety and depression is a large proportion of participants are widows and divorced with 56.7% and 55.2%. This indicates that lonely elderly are more wiliness to use technology and improve their QoL (Pires et al., 2022).

On the other hand, telehealth has no effect on all marital statuses with self-care, pain, or discomfort due to the complexity of long-standing diseases that need medical intervention (WHO,

2021).

5.2.2.5 Living agreement with QoL

The living arrangement of the user of telehealth service significantly influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, anxiety, or depression (H18-H20-H21) by using Chi-Square or Fisher's Exact Test ($p < 0.001$). The result confirmed a correlation between the two, where a significant correlation was supported. More than 54% of the elderly who lived alone reported that telehealth decreased their anxiety and depression. Meanwhile, 42% of the respondents who lived with others expressed that telehealth reduces their anxiety and depression.

A similar positive and significant association has supported this outcome in a study conducted in Germany about the effect of telehealth on the elderly with or without psychological illness (Lang et al., 2021). Lonely elderly are more prone to be isolated with psychological distress, and telehealth mitigates their mood and emotional distress (Arnedt et al., 2021). Additionally, survey results implied the respondents who lived alone also reported that using telehealth helped them move more often by 87.5%; for patients living alone, the statistics revealed 75.6%, and for those who lived with a partner and other caregivers, 56.4%. Further results from the survey of the respondent to the usual activity found telehealth increased it among elderly who lived alone 84.3%, with a partner only 66% and partners with other carers 48% indicate lonely older people have time to participate in cultural, social activity and walking (Lang et al., 2021; Valdivieso et al., 2018).

On the other hand, this study found no statistically significant associations between the living arrangement of the user of telehealth services and self-care, pain, or discomfort (H19-H21). Most elderly patients noted 70-80% that telehealth did not affect their pain and discomfort. Likewise, all patients reported that telehealth did not affect their self-care. However, variations exist due to functional and psychological disability in older adults contributing to their physical well-being and dependence on self-care activity (Cohen et al., 2006).

5.2.2.6 Dependency with QoL

The survey findings indicate the dependency of the user of telehealth services influences the relationship between using telehealth services and elderly mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or

depression by using Chi-Square or Fisher's Exact Test ($p < 0.001$) (H121-H23-H25). Which states that individuals who presented to the clinic by wheel-chair telehealth did not affect their mobility by 59.5%, compared to those who attended the clinic walked in it improved their mobility by 84.2%.

In this regard, the findings also reveal that usual activities increase with more independent patients by 77.2% and only 5.4% of dependent elderly. In addition, the Cramer V test showed a strong correlation between the dependency of telehealth users on mobility and usual activity. This finding correlates with other studies (Wong et al., 2022; Barenfeld et al., 2020). The elderly with chronic diseases are linked directly with the performance of health status of the elderly as aging nature leads to degenerative process alter in mobility and activity of the patients. The elderly who depends on a caregiver is less to move compared to the active elderly.

The findings also indicate that 51% reported telehealth decreased anxiety and depression among independent elderly. In contrast, 33% of walk-ins conveyed that telehealth decreased their depression or anxiety; this conclusion is in line with the fact that telehealth has more effect in reducing anxiety or depression in dependent elderly. They suffer from low self-esteem, increasing inability to perform daily tasks, loss of autonomy, lack of energy, and prefer to stay at home to decrease the burden on another caregiver (Kaveh et al., 2021).

In this regard, the findings demonstrate that the dependency of the users does influence the relationship between using telehealth and elderly self-care, pain, or discomfort (H22, H24). The finding of this research is not supported as 99.8% of the respondents expressed that the system does not affect self-care, and 74.3% do not affect their pain or discomfort due to complications of long-standing diseases affecting their physical wellbeing (Lopez et al., 2021).

5.2.2.7 Usability & Acceptance of Telehealth with QoL.

As hypothesized, the expected effect of acceptance of telehealth in elderly QoL has a positive correlation with elderly mobility (H28). The data result demonstrates positive influences between the Acceptance of the user of telehealth and elderly mobility. The Anova-test is an appropriate hypothesis testing (Anova Test $p < 0.005$). The result confirmed a significant correlation was supported and confirmed with Jelsma & Maart (2015) acceptance of telehealth through mobile-friendly access with the availability of appointments in a comfortable environment enhances their

QoL. It motivates them to walk and move more when older adults are traditionally reluctant to accept innovative telehealth and easily engage with technology (Cimperman et al., 2016).

Conversely, the acceptance of the user of telehealth does not influence the relationship between acceptance of telehealth and elderly self-care, usual activity, pain or discomfort, and anxiety or depression, as (Anova test $p>0.005$) failed to accept the hypothesis (H29- H30-H31-H32). The outcome of this research is clarified by Kalicki et al. (2021) as most elderly with long-standing diseases with physical disabilities, cognitive decline, motor, and bone dysfunction, in addition to technical anxiety and resistance to change traditional methods. All potential barriers to dealing with technology alter the improvement of their activity, mood, and pain.

The usability of telehealth significantly positively correlates with elderly mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or depression (H2, H4, H6). The ANOVA test is an appropriate hypothesis testing (ANOVA Test $p<0.005$) as presented in Table 4.9. The result confirmed a significant correlation was supported and confirmed with (Jelsma & Maart, 2015). Ease of use of safe and secure telehealth through easy-friendly technology with the availability of appointments in a comfortable environment enhances their QoL and decreases computer anxiety (Pires et al., 2022). It motivates them to walk and engage in social activity and self-care (Pires et al., 2022). Older adults have a positive attitude toward technology-supported activities (K. Chen & Chan, 2011). On the other hand, the usability of telehealth does not affect elderly self-care and pain or discomfort (ANOVA Test $p>0.005$) due to complications of long-standing diseases affecting their physical and psychological wellbeing (Lopez et al., 2021).

The findings reveal that increase acceptance and usability of telehealth more for the elderly with lower educational levels ($p<0.040$) and dependent ($p<0.006$) by using the average mean of the ANOVA Test. In this regard, dependency, in particular, positively affects patient acceptance and usability of telehealth. This research result meets the study in China by Zhou et al. (2019) that meets the same conclusion, more dependent and less educated are prone to a willingness to adapt and accept telehealth as it's easy in practical application and software design. In addition to adding value, they need technology as it makes their life easier, secure, and safe (Markert, Sasangohar, et al., 2021)

5.2.2.8 Trust in the Telehealth System & Availability of the devices

Regarding trust, the interview result showed that 85% of respondents believed that both clinics and telehealth got the same amount of trust. One participant recommended a comfortable environment to increase trust in telehealth. Three participants suggested effective communication by building doctor rapport using verbal and nonverbal clues such as body language, eye contact, voice tone, and empathy to improve the clinic and telehealth level of trust.

Finally, one of the participants thought telehealth interferes with communication as health professionals can express only facial language, unlike in an actual visit, as physicians can assess the entire body language. Tsai (2014) suggests in the Social Capital Model value of patients' trust in health care industries to encourage the use of the health services, patient compliance, and treatment submission.

Regarding the appropriate device used during a telehealth consultation. Six physicians mentioned that the best device is a smartphone, and one believed a computer device is the best effect. One physician stated that different devices such as computers, mobile phones, and I-Pad could be used for successful telehealth consultation. Two mentioned some challenges regarding internet speed deficiency in hospitals compared to patients' side, which differs from one company to another.

Zhou et al. (2019) suggest that network and device availability influence users' acceptance of telehealth. May et al. (2021) argue that poor internet network connectivity impacts the quality of telehealth consultation due to delays in transmitting health information between health professionals and patients.

5.2.3 Challenges and suggestions

A discussion of the findings related to the challenges of the perception of the elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their QoL. The interviewer addressed the most concerning challenges. Eight of the participants believed that the physical impairment of the elderly such as hearing and visual loss with difficulty in physical examination, the most challenges faced during a telehealth consultation is lack of physical examination elderly need the interviewers' concerns about telehealth have the same similarities of barriers that address in many articles (Steindal et al., 2021; Zulfiqar et al., 2019).

The three participants suggested the adopted elderly mobile home clinic conduct a physical

examination of the elderly. As discussed in the literature review, many contemporary studies have demonstrated that telehealth supported by mobile home visits enhances the effectiveness of the telehealth system (Kruse et al., 2020). Indeed, the findings denote that from the perspective of primary health care, several managerial and enforcement measures should be undertaken to improve the telehealth services uptake by elderly individuals.

Four other participants said technical instability, such as connectivity network alter in a successful telehealth consultation, and two participants recommended increasing network capacity. To overcome the technical and internet network limitation in primary health care, the findings demonstrate the need for a more extensive and detailed capacity of telecommunication companies and establishing collaborations with private companies. This result signifies the need for a qualification in telecommunication personnel distributed in health centers to prepare them to work with telehealth caregivers (Lopez et al., 2021).

In addition, four interviewees explained that the elderly forgot their appointment times, and many physicians received missed calls while contacting their patients. Three of the participants recommend reminding elderly patients about their appointment times. Similarly, three participants explained the difficulty of finding patients' telephone numbers in the electronic personnel file, and one participant suggested updating the telehealth users' electronic personal information. N. Chen & Liu (2022) indicate that several innovative strategies could improve telehealth services.

Two participants raised this issue regarding the elderly acceptance of technology, and three of the participants suggested improving the acceptance of telehealth through conducting awareness sessions and providing educational videos and training courses for the users. The current study finding aligns with Tsai (2014), concluding that health-related motivation positively influences acceptance of telehealth use.

Regarding communication barriers, two participants stated that there was a lack of verbal and non-verbal communication during the consultation as patients had difficulty showing body language. Mentioned two of the participants said that language barriers play an important challenge during telehealth visits to improve the difficulty in communication. Two of the interviewees suggested facilitating an artificial intelligent-supported telehealth system. These findings in the current study meet the conclusion of a study conducted in the UK by Papoutsi et al. (2020) on artificial intelligence optimizing the effectiveness of using telehealth services.

Finally, six participants recommended 24 hours telehealth consultation, and four highlighted the importance of developing and offering a multidisciplinary clinic to enhance different health specialties for elderly patients. Giordano et al. (2016) suggest multidisciplinary telehealth to reduce fall prevention for elderly patients.

5.2.4 Overall Discussion

In general, the quantitative study findings are consistent with several studies; the results showed that telehealth improved patients' mobility, usual activities, and anxiety or depression. However, in contrast to the reported studies, the results of the present study revealed no impact of telehealth on patients' self-care, pain, or discomfort, while in a qualitative study, feedback that telehealth effect elderly pain or discomfort, usual activity, and anxiety or depression. The dimensions cited less were mobility and the elderly's self-care, as most interviewees were from medical staff who have a vital role in prescribing medication, and mental counselling, while mobility, and self-care, in their opinion, need more physical assessment.

The oldest elderly are more likely to report improved psychological symptoms like anxiety and depression, while the young and middle elderly are more likely to benefit physically. Highly educated patients reported more mobility and usual activity improvements than other educational levels. In contrast, other measures of QoL like pain or discomfort and anxiety or depression were relatively similar among all levels of education groups. The sex of elderly patients who participated in this study was male more than female, significantly improving anxiety and depression. In contrast, sex had no effect on other QoL dimensions.

Single and divorced elderly patients were more likely to improve mobility and usual activity; divorced and widowed patients reported decreased anxiety and depression. Moreover, elderly who lives alone reported a more positive impact on their mobility, usual activity, and mood condition while using telehealth. On the other hand, this study found no statistically significant associations between the living arrangement of the user of telehealth services and self-care, pain, or discomfort of the patient. Moreover, mobility and usual activity are more likely to significantly impact independent patients compared to dependent elderly. While mood thought positively affected dependent people.

The usability of telehealth significantly correlates with elderly mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or depression, while acceptance of telehealth technology positively impacts patients' mobility.

Most respondents believed that both clinics and telehealth have the same trust. Nonetheless, suggestions to improve communications and minimize challenges like internet speed and physical examination of high-risk patients should be addressed. These include adopting an elderly mobile home clinic, increasing network capacity, establishing collaborations with private telecommunication companies, and launching 24 hours telehealth consultation service.

In summary, those patients who live alone with higher educational achievements and the oldest elderly are more likely to benefit from telehealth. Challenges of the service are available and should be addressed as appropriate.

5.2.5 Managerial Recommendations

The findings of this study have several important managerial implications. One of the strategic goals of primary health care is to improve telehealth that affects elderly QoL.

5.2.5.1 Overcome the Shortage of Human Resources and strengthen Telehealth Clinic

To overcome the shortage of qualified professional medical staff due to the voluntary retirement scheme and COVID 19 opening center and work overload with lack of availability of appointments at local health centers. In Addition to the growing phenomenon of an ageing society and the implementation of telehealth for this age group who are frequent attendance to the health care centers and rehospitalization as a complication of their health and social conditions, applying such technology is cost-effective for primary health care by early detection of health behavior for elderly patients. This group of patients with a higher incidence of chronic diseases involves extensive utilization of health resources., So virtual geriatric clinics will enhance the reallocation of health resources that meet the increasing demand for health and social services and improve elderly autonomy even with multi-morbidity. Additionally, find the solution to usual human resources shortages. The proposal suggests that primary Health Care offers an action plan to overcome the problems:

- Recruit new health professionals part-time and work from home contracts to conduct telehealth.
- Comprehensive, collaborative health team in the multidisciplinary clinic: develop shared experiences and roles with a more flexible range of transferable skills and flexible changes in

a different care setting through the comprehensive clinic with different specialties of interprofessional teams from primary and secondary care (Giordano et al., 2016). The intervention included coproduction by teams that differed in composition from one site to another through (Telehealth modalities); this can be successful enhancement through training schemes (Gardenier et al., 2021).

- Twenty-four hours telehealth clinic provides accessibility and continuity of care.

5.2.5.2 Smart Home Environment

Smart home environment: connection of devices and sensors with the elderly smart, innovative home community to measure their mobility as bathing, preparing meals, watching TV, sitting on the sofa, and monitoring activity of daily life activity, which reflects the health status of elderly patients. This application describes the elderly activity as time, location, and injuries, sharing results and data uploaded to cloud storage to represent it to a health professional (Beale & Jaruzel, 2017).

5.2.5.3 Telehealth Occupational Therapy

As decreased self-care in research finding as an elderly individual has difficulty performing daily living activities such as cooking, dressing, and bathing, home evaluation needs to be monitoring by occupational therapists to meet ageing demand and enhance community-based care to continue the elderly to live safely at home. In addition, enter a partnership with funding charities in the community to provide structural changes, installation of a grab bar or ramp, and devices like a fire alarm, glucose monitoring sensor, and wheelchair. Finally, educational videos for recording any activities problems at home and uploaded to be reviewed by occupational therapy (RENDA & LAPE, 2018).

5.2.5.4 Regulation and Telehealth Policies

- Primary health care needs to raise policies and update guidelines used for both health care providers and patients inaccessible of the secure process to create a trustworthy environment.
- Create a funding framework to promote innovation, coding of incentives, and policy issues related to incentives to emphasize best practices.

- Affordability for the individual might require a strategic change in the funding model as telehealth services will be charged with health autonomy in the future.
- Telehealth should be considered part of the overall strategy for developing care services. Development plans should have the Joint Strategic Needs Assessment. Pathway redevelopment should be managed with comprehensive involvement from all those concerned with delivering the care pathway and policies in practicing telehealth. Application of local forum supervises clinical governance of health provider and hospital indicators and discusses it regularly.

Table 5.1 Policies to support Telehealth in the Kingdom of Bahrain

Title	Policies to support Telehealth in the Kingdom of Bahrain
Main Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <u>Incentive Policies:</u> broad sweeping policies and reimbursement which are aimed to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase beneficiaries' access to care. • Focus on decreasing barriers needed to practice telehealth among the kingdom through conducting a research study and multiple streams frameworks. ➤ <u>Privacy policies:</u> the policy describes the data collected from patients, use and disclose the information related to medical illness through secure professional PC password & ID identification for patients and their guardian, not use and disclose health information for marketing purposes, free services in a government hospital (out of pocket). Establish the responsible storage of data and different electronic records decentralized for clinical medical records, and all patients are aware of their responsibilities and rights(Chang et al., 2021). ➤ Environment-focused strategy provides an evidence-based guide and describes needs. Monitoring and evaluation are essential to measuring efficacy, utility, and level of acceptance and account for any expenses.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Labour market policy disrupted job productivity and security during the pandemic of Covid-19, loss of payroll of elective procedures. Several policies help mitigate the economic impact of employees, and financial support policy cushions against job losses, so telehealth sustains revenue stream.
<p>Objectives of main policies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Primary Health Care has witnessed the introduction of telehealth in many government hospitals parallel with private health agencies. Providing licensing policy “qualified provider” from NHRA to health care providers related to legislation and addressing various potential issues and privacy, confidentiality, cost, and quality. Physician trend reports include regulatory compensation, impact and reimbursement, and employee and patient satisfaction. Numbers of KPIs documented and compared with international trending (<i>Elderly Care - Ministry of Health, 2020</i>). ➤ Corporate effective innovation strategy with a shared vision between different health organizations. ➤ Telehealth is also a viable strategy to improve employee and hospital performance by utilizing electronic modalities combining telehealth into a value-based, patient care model by utilising technology that associates patients with providers and professional to professional. ➤ Audits and policy identify potential environmental benefits associated with telehealth. Health care industries lack sustainable development practices due to fear of additional regulation and cost, so adopting carbon-reducing activity turns health industries green. ➤ Hospital performance Policy an increasing number of hospitals are using telehealth in Bahrain. Organizational performance by developing productivity, improving profitability, and decreasing costs. Hospitals are dependent on telehealth frameworks to help them gain a competitive advantage. Studies indicate that telehealth resources positively impact an organization’s competitive advantage and position in the marketplace. Prior

studies recommend that telehealth services offer a digital advantage to a clinic leading to organizational benefits such as productivity, cost, and patient and personal quality outcomes. They may also use technology to motivate medical expertise (providers) and patients. Improving the efficiency of care leads to better care coordination, increased decision making, and diminishing expense of care in four domains: (a) clinical outcomes domain; (b) stakeholder and community engagement domain; (c) safety and security domain; and (d) efficiency and decrease cost domain in terms of saving resources in different departments. The multilevel regression model studies the influence of telehealth service on hospital performance, demonstrating a high score in efficiency and cost reduction in hospitals using telehealth compared to hospitals without implementation of telehealth strategy (*Healthcare*, n.d.).

Improving hospitals' performance by enhancing and ambidextrously balancing exploration and exploitation capabilities through asset digitalization.

➤ **Medication Policy** NHRA provides rules and regulations to physicians instructing them not to prescribe any medication through telehealth which includes:

- Anticancer Drugs
- Narcotics include codeine and morphine(*Elderly Care - Ministry of Health*, 2020).

5.2.5.5 Net Work Articulture and Telehealth Resource Center

To ensure efficient and effective communication between health providers and elderly patients, a surge in demand for primary health care through the existing network infrastructure in all departments at health centers to meet the network traffic congestion. Applying software-defined networks to support telehealth. Provide office for the advancement of telehealth, and these centers prepare telehealth programs resource development which contains modules in telehealth operation,

regulatory and legal consideration, reimbursement, marketing, and employee training(Ni et al., 2016).

5.2.5.6 Innovative Patient Self-care Automated Process

The innovative process in the elderly using telehealth to achieve higher efficiency and less costly services through a patient self-care automation system. Telehealth poses solutions to challenges such as the growing demand for health services, the aging population, or the need to manage large amounts of information. Although the possibility of involving families and friends as partners in digital platforms thus enhances a strategy for sustaining patient-physician partnerships. To encourage preventive measures and approaches in primary care services, adopt new regulations, and design a unique atmosphere or ecosystem for innovative health centers(Banbury et al., 2018).

Strong Management support with the engagement of stakeholders. Additionally, the processes were developed and planned within the rationalization of primary health care resources. The Table below presents the innovative telehealth consultation process and the outcome:

Table 5.2 Innovative Telehealth Consultation Automated Process and Outcomes

Innovative telehealth process	Outcomes /Results
Artificial intelligence through an online appointment system to book appointments for telehealth consultation by entering only patient CPR and artificial intelligence through voice conversation by answering the chatbot checklist to complete the process.	To select suitable appointment telehealth time and filter emergencies from non-emergencies cases.
Comprehensive telehealth clinics with different medical specialties and lunch between primary and secondary care.	One-Stop-Shop Consultation.
Develop a media plan to raise awareness and educate elderly patients on telehealth services to enhance efficiency and obtain the necessary health care.	Early detection and health promotion as cost-effective for detecting diseases in their early stages.

Launch of a smartphone application and artificial intelligence that monitors patients' vital signs in a telehealth system.

Motivate the elderly for a healthier lifestyle.
 Trusted source and accuracy of health information.
 Improve the quality of life.

A brief SWOT analysis of the effect of telehealth services on QoL for elderly high-risk patients is presented in Figure 5.1. It's conducted to focus on the areas that may promote or hinder the managerial application to improve the QoL of elderly patients that use telehealth services in primary health care.

<p><u>Strength</u> Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I-Seha electronic medical file • Training Center • Extent development of medical knowledge and practice • Establish independent regulatory bodies like NHRA and health center internal and external auditing. • Availability of human resources of expert health professionals. • Acceptable behavior to use innovation by the patients. 	<p><u>Weakness</u> Need Improvement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ineffective appointment system • Lack of elderly empowerment like training and education to use telehealth • Lack of telehealth links between different hospitals, research centers, and academics • No regulatory framework for data privacy, security, and safety. • Fear of loss a specific job when the telehealth system is activated. • Lack of workflow reengineering initiatives to cope with telehealth network applications. • Absent of evaluation and benchmarking scheme for telehealth.
<p><u>Opportunities</u> Chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of expert staff exchange programs. • Telehealth could be a part of e.Government. • There is a new trend of telehealth in medicine (preventive medicine, mobile application, early detection medicine, and cybersecurity). • The social network can educate and conduct awareness session programs. • Telehealth offers new careers involving skillful professionals. • The telehealth business model takes the initiative from the private sector. 	<p><u>Threats</u> Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase prevalence of non-communicable diseases among the elderly. • Competition between private and government health centers in advance to use telehealth. • Demographic changes. • Lack of sustainable business model for telehealth. • Lack of incorporation of the strategic plan in Biomedical information in the medical education system. • According to regulation, there is a lack of stakeholder commitment to take part in responsibilities in utilizing telehealth. • Lack of cross-platform with different artificial intelligence for elderly user-friendly application.

*Figure 5.1 Telehealth Services Used by Elderly Patients in Primary Health Care
SWOT Analysis (Hussein & Khalifa, 2012)*

Managerial recommendation for innovation telehealth project was adopted to enhance elderly experiences to improve their QoL on descriptive analysis and prospective staff analysis results. But, Conversely, the decision-maker in primary health care resolves some of the fundamental issues that might significantly impact patients' QoL. Strong management support joined with stakeholder engagement & coordination (patients, nurses, physicians & media) is required to address these issues. Moreover, overcoming staff shortages, offering training programs, implementing performance incentives, and sharing knowledge and experiences may help to boost elderly motivation to use telehealth services, eventually resulting in better patient quality of care (Ciasullo, 2017). Lastly, a strong electronic system with a network cloud supported by artificial intelligent needs to be implemented to achieve higher efficiency in the new change management process and policies.

5.2.6 Research Limitations

This study's limitations include the following:

- There was a lack of previous local and regional studies on similar topics; only a few studies assessed the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their quality of life; most studies found it was a comparison between two groups of traditional and innovation or one group in pre and post telehealth use, it suggested that the service is relatively new in the field and needs to be investigated further.
- The main limitation is the research focused on the conceptual model of the survey, not on the demographic characteristics and other moderating factors, which are conceded to be a rich source of data. Knowledge management should be applied to utilise the data most efficiently and effectively in public administration and decision-making.
- Moderate heterogeneity was identified among studies that measured depression, mental components, and the physical QoL, which need a long time and special medical tool for assessment.

- The European Quality of Life did not include items related to the behavioral intentions of elderly patients to use telehealth systems services. For future research, this aspect must be discretely used with the European Quality of Life for future research.
- The data used in this study were collected mainly in five big health centers in the kingdom of Bahrain. From the perspective of data reliability and integrity, it should also include older adults in small villages, then a cross-national study involving comparative analysis can be conducted.

5.2.7 Future Research

What is now needed is a cross-national study involving telehealth clinics of government sectors in primary and secondary care to promote a general perspective and comprehensive analysis, especially the Bahrain health system moves towards autonomy and health insurance. In addition, it is necessary to benchmark the results with other countries' findings. In addition, decision-maker leadership should broaden collaborative telehealth policies at organizational levels to ensure the growth of telehealth capacity and sustained funding.

To achieve high-quality telehealth services, regular quality assurance and performance measurements should be applied continuously to promote the effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

Bahrain's primary health system has significantly accomplished and witnessed comprehensive health innovation technology. Recently, the Supreme Council of Health (SCH), responsible for supervising the engineering and technical requirements of health facilities, NHRA provides health regulation for telehealth standards and licensing of primary health care. All the government health entities to move forward towards autonomy and health insurance schemes (*Sustainable Development*, n.d.). Therefore, it is important to adopt telehealth technology for elderly patients. Telehealth enhances regular chronic disease management from the formal health care framework by developing patient self-awareness and knowledge via "expert patient" programs. The ageing process will parallel an escalation in the implementation of telehealth missions to encourage patients to improve their QoL.

A mixed-method approach was used in this research. The data for this study were collected from 627 elderly patients using the Euro QoL & usability and acceptance questionnaire for telehealth. Survey to assess the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their QoL. Moreover, 20 semi-structured interviews were conducted with medical staff members and patients to gain their views and perspectives in a comprehensive picture of understanding of telehealth services. The mixed methodology approach facilitated the researcher to present various stakeholders' opinions and experiences and offer a rationale on the extent of the European QoL, Usability, and Acceptance Questionnaire to improve digitalization in healthcare system practices.

Descriptive statistics revealed that the average age of the participants was 70.31 ± 8.22 years; more than half of the 56.0% aged between 60 and 69 years, approximately 30% were between 70 and 79 years, and 15.7% aged above 80 years. While most participants were married, 58.7%, only 5.8% of them were single. Divorced and widowed participants constituted 19.3% and 16.2% of the participants, respectively. Regarding the educational level, approximately half of the participants had a primary school level of 45.0%. Patients with college degrees constituted only 20% of the participants. Up to 88% of the patients presented to the health care facility as walk-in patients, and only 12% presented using a wheelchair. It can also be observed that most patients living alone reached 41.3%, at least (30%, and 28.7% only with a partner and with both the partner

and another carer, respectively). Almost all participants had diabetes mellitus 97.2%, and almost 69% were hypertensive; the least prevalent comorbidity was Joint or osteoporosis 21.3 %, followed by respiratory diseases 9%.

The statistical result revealed a positive relationship between using telehealth services and elderly quality of life in some dimensions. For example, using telehealth services improved mobility by 75%, increased the usual activity dimension by 68.3%, and decreased the anxiety or depression in the elderly's quality of life by 35%. At the same time, telehealth services had no effects on the self-care by 99.8% and pain or discomfort dimension in the elderly's quality of life by 74.3%, as 25% of the participants reported a good effect (telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort). In addition to semi-structured interviews of 20 medical staff and patients, explore their telehealth experience in elderly high-risk patients in their QoL. During the interview, telehealth affected different dimensions of QoL. The majority of the respondents, 95%, reported it improved elderly pain or discomfort, 90% stated that it improved usual activity, and 75% showed that telehealth affected anxiety and depression. While 55 % showed improvement in elderly mobility, only 45% of respondents noted elderly self-care was affected.

Correlation between using telehealth services and elderly quality of statistical life results revealed significant influences in some dimensions with demographic data. For example, telehealth services improved mobility with age group, marital status, living arrangement, educational level, and dependency as well as usual activity, and decreased the anxiety or depression in the elderly's quality of life in relation to all demographic data. At the same time, telehealth services had no effects on the self-care dimension in the elderly's quality of life and no effect on the pain or discomfort dimension in the elderly's quality of life through 25% of the participants reported a good effect (telehealth decreased their pain and discomfort). SPSS chi-Square, Fisher Exact Test, and Cremer test were used.

Inferential analysis results strongly affect the usability of telehealth system in QoL dimensions showed significant correlation with (Anova Test p -value <0.001) with mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or depression, while not significant with self-care and pain or discomfort dimensions. Elderly Acceptance of technology positively affected mobility by ANOVA test $p < 0.005$ while not significant with the other four QoL dimensions. Correlation of demographic data with Average mean of usability and acceptance of telehealth (ANOVA Test $p < 0.005$) was

found to be significant with low educational levels and dependent elderly patients.

Regarding trust, the interview result showed that 85% of respondents believed that both clinics and telehealth got the same amount of trust regarding the appropriate device used during a telehealth consultation. Six physicians mentioned that the best device is a smartphone, and one believed a computer device is the best effective. One physician stated that different devices such as computers, mobile phones, and I-Pad could be used for successful telehealth consultation. Two mentioned some challenges regarding internet speed deficiency in hospitals compared to patients' side, which differs from one company to another.

In general, studies show that the integration between patient and medical staff experiences and opinions will help to understand the perception of elderly high-risk patients of using telehealth services on their QoL. Based on the study's findings, a number of managerial recommendations were proposed; emphasis has been placed on redesigning the telehealth platform to enjoy greater efficiency and effectiveness. The research findings generated beneficial, productive information that enhanced to overcome many of the encountered issues. Many medical staff members suggested innovation recommendations that can be considered with managerial primary health care considerations, such as multidisciplinary telehealth platform, smart home environment, regulation, telehealth policies, network agriculture and telehealth resource center, and Innovative patient self-care automated process.

Finally, it may be worth revealing that the data findings will propose a digital framework for geriatric clinics and possibly opportunities to formulate new research questions and present the practical usefulness for primary health care and elderly QoL protocol. Furthermore, another opportunity is to develop the research scope in the future to evaluate and compare the findings and benchmark with other countries in GCC and worldwide. Yet, the data was managed and revealed interesting findings, providing ground for a broader spectrum of future studies.

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Glossary of terms

Telehealth

Telemonitoring

Telecoaching

Telemedicine

Tele exercise

Perception

Elderly

High Risk

Quality of Life

Mobility

Usual Activity

Self-care

Pain or Discomfort

Anxiety or Depression

List of abbreviations

ADL	Activities of Daily Life
ASCOT	Adult Social Care Outcomes Toolkit
ASU	Actual System Use
AtU	Attitude towards Using
BI	Behavioural Intention to Use
CA	Computer Anxiety
Covid-19	Coronavirus Disease
DOC	Doctor's Opinion
DM	Diabetes Mellitus
EE	Effort Expectancy
EQ-5D	European Quality – 5 Dimensions
DQoL	Disease Quality of Life
FC	Facilitating Conditions
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council

HRQoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
HTN	Hypertension
PEoU	Perceived Ease of Use
PE	Performance Expectancy
PHC	Primary Health Centre
PU	Perceived Usefulness
PS	Perceived Security
QoL	Quality of Life
RCT	Random Control Trial
RPM	Remote Patient Monitoring
SCRQoL	Social Care Related Quality of Life
SI	Social Influence
SWOT	Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TS	Telehealth Services
TMA	Telemonitoring Application
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance & Use of Technology
VAS	Visual Analogue Scale
WHOQOL-BREF	abbreviated World Health Organization Quality of Life
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
MAXQDA	Max Weber and ends-QDA-Qualitative Data analysis
PC	Personal Computer
ID	Identity Documents
SCH	Supreme Council of Health
KPI	Keep Performance Indicator
NHRA	National Health Regulatory Authority

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Abstract

The telehealth platform is crucial to improving the elderly's quality of life in primary healthcare. This study explores the impact of elderly high-risk patients' quality of life achieved by using telehealth. The study adopts a mixed method. The first 627 patients' opinions are surveyed to answer the online questionnaire using the European quality of life tool and usability and acceptance questionnaire related to the telehealth system. Second, a semi-structured interview is used with 20 staff members and patients from primary health clinics. The inferential analysis results found correlation affected the usability of the telehealth system in QoL dimensions. They showed a significant correlation (Anova Test $p < 0.001$) with mobility, usual activity, and anxiety or depression, while not significant with self-care and pain or discomfort dimensions, similar to QoL with demographic data. While in qualitative data, the interview results showed that telehealth affected different dimensions of QoL. Most respondents (95%) were engaged in usual activities, and 75% indicated that telehealth affected anxiety and depression. While 55% showed improvement in elderly mobility, only 45% of respondents noted that elderly self-care was affected. Some of the challenges and recommendations the participants addressed were to improve the telehealth system in primary health care.

Regarding trust, the interview results showed that 85% of respondents believed that both clinics and telehealth got the same amount of trust. Respondents revealed some challenges such as

physical impairment, difficulty conducting physical examinations, technical instability, lack of communication, language barriers, decreased acceptance of technology by elderly patients, and perception of the elderly using telehealth services in their QoL recommendation. The respondents suggested the availability of 24-hour telehealth for emergency cases, multidisciplinary telehealth clinics, and elderly mobile clinics connected with telehealth. The research recommends introducing innovative applications to enhance patient autonomy, overcoming staff shortages, and offering the elderly educational training courses that address their concerns.

Keywords

Telehealth, elderly, Quality of Life, Digital platform, Technology Acceptance Model, European QoL, Mixed methods.

Résumé

Aujourd'hui la télésanté est essentielle pour améliorer la qualité de vie des personnes âgées dans les soins de santé primaires. Cette étude explore l'impact de la qualité de vie des patients âgés à haut risque obtenue grâce à l'utilisation de la télésanté. L'étude adopte une méthode mixte. 627 premières opinions des patients sont interrogées pour répondre au questionnaire en ligne à l'aide de l'outil européen de qualité de vie et du questionnaire de convivialité et d'acceptation lié au système de télésanté. Deuxièmement, un entretien semi-directif avec 20 membres composé de personnel de santé et des patients de cliniques de santé primaires. Les résultats de l'analyse inférentielle ont montré une corrélation affectée la facilité d'utilisation du système de télésanté dans les dimensions de la Qualité de Vie. Ils ont montré une corrélation significative (Test Anova p 0,001) avec la mobilité, l'activité habituelle et l'anxiété ou la dépression, alors qu'elle n'était pas significative avec les soins personnels et les dimensions de douleur ou d'inconfort, similaire à la qualité de vie avec les données démographiques. Les résultats des données qualitatives ont montré que la télésanté touchent différentes dimensions de la qualité de vie. La plupart des répondants (95 %) pratiquaient des activités habituelles et 75 % ont montré que la télésanté affectait l'anxiété et la dépression. Alors que 55 % ont montré une amélioration de la mobilité des personnes âgées, seulement 45 % des répondants ont noté que les soins personnels des personnes âgées étaient affectés.

En ce qui concerne la confiance, les résultats de l'entrevue ont montré que 85 % des répondants croyaient que les cliniques et la télésanté recevaient la même confiance. Les répondants ont révélé certains défis tels que la déficience physique, la difficulté à effectuer des examens physiques, l'instabilité technique, le manque de communication, les barrières linguistiques, la diminution de l'acceptation de la technologie par les patients âgés et la perception des personnes âgées utilisant les services de télésanté dans leur recommandation de Qualité de Vie. Les répondants ont suggéré la disponibilité de la télésanté 24 heures sur 24 pour les cas d'urgence, les cliniques de télésanté multidisciplinaires et les cliniques mobiles pour personnes âgées liées à la télésanté. La recherche recommande d'introduire des applications innovantes pour améliorer l'autonomie des patients, surmonter les pénuries de personnel et offrir aux personnes âgées des cours de formation qui répondent à leurs préoccupations.

Mots clés

Télésanté, personnes âgées, Qualité de vie, Plateforme numérique, Modèle d'acceptation technologique, Qualité de vie européenne, Méthodes mixtes.